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P I pipelines and

Pipedreams

**THE CRISES AND THE FUTURES OF
ANTIBIOTIC DRUG DEVELOPMENT**

**Roundtable held on
8 November 2024
in Strasbourg (Lieu d'Europe)**

Pipelines and Pipedreams

The Crises and the Futures of Antibiotic Drug Development

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The past futures of antibiotics

Christoph Gradmann¹, Mirza Alas Portillio, Claas Kirchhelle, Jørgen J. Leisner, Erin L. Paterson, Maria Santesmases, Frédéric Vagneron, Mingyuan Zhang Betancourt

For thirty years, there have been many laments about the end of antibiotics. These laments have taken many forms: That of a failure of drug innovation, a lack of profitability, an environmental crisis, shifting global markets, among which antimicrobial resistance is the most relevant, or best analysed. Each of these follows a logic of absence and scarcity, which eulogizes an imagined golden age of wonder drugs and the vanishing of infections, insisting that the main problem of our present is the absence of new antibiotics. The metaphor of an empty antibiotic drug pipeline is the perfect expression of this. If nothing flows in them, pipelines are useless. The biggest problem, as the metaphor suggests, is the absence of new antibiotics - rather than the abundance of older antibiotics as generics.

But, as we can learn from Roland Barthes' classical critique of metaphors in political language, the main quality of stories told in a metaphor is that they present objects and circumstances as facts of nature that should better be seen as a result of human activity (Barthes 1972). What is this human activity when it comes to the empty drug pipeline for antibiotics, how did the empty pipeline come about, and how appropriate is this metaphor for describing the challenges with regards to antibiotic drug development? These were the questions that formed the basis of a conversation between Christoph Gradmann and Jørgen J. Leisner, which began in 2017 and expanded in 2019 to include María Jesús Santesmases, Claas Kirchhelle, and Frédéric Vagneron. As a team, their interest and work formed the basis of an application for funding that was sent to the Research Council of Norway in spring 2020. The success of the application led to the research project "How did the Antibiotic Pipeline Run Dry (DryAp)?" (NFR314490).

The closing conference of the DryAp project, held in the University of Strasbourg in November 2024 took a form reminiscent of a witness seminar. The round table discussions documented in this publication reflect the experiences, concerns, and hopes of the participants: key stakeholders in the field of antibiotic research and development from the industry, funding and regulatory agencies, and partnerships recently created under the inspiration of transnational organisations such as the *Médecins Sans Frontières* (MSF). The participants were invited by the DryAp project to discuss the challenges and resistances they have experienced in the evaluation, development, production, and circulation of new antibiotics. They were particularly encouraged to reflect on the policies, institutions, funding mechanisms, and inequalities shaping the process of bringing new antibiotics to market today. The rich material gathered from the discussions reveals that the "antibiotic pipeline" metaphor, despite its historical origin, remains highly relevant today. Its enduring significance points to a whole set of issues related to the global AMR crisis, and the urgent need to confront these challenges through broad and effective policies that support innovation.

Rather than taking the metaphor for granted, the DryAp project aimed to historicise and contextualise the dynamics that gave rise to the "empty antibiotic pipeline" metaphor and shaped its revolution. What was it that started with a certain disenchantment with empirical

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screening for antibiotic compounds in the 1970s and ended with Big Pharma deserting the field of anti-infective drug development at large shortly after 2000? (Alas Portillo, Gómez Rodríguez, et al. 2024)² The roundtable discussion documented here is a contribution to that story. It departs from a recollection of events from stakeholders directly involved in antibiotic research and development from the 1980s to today. Furthermore, it provides perspective and elucidation on the work that has emerged from the five work packages within the DryAP project with doctoral dissertations and post-graduate research conducted by: Mirza Alas Portillo (Alas Portillo 2025), Isabel María Gómez Rodríguez, Laura D. Martinenghi (Martinenghi 2024), Erin L. Paterson (Paterson 2025), and Belma Skender.

Point of departure

The DryAP Project began with seven key presuppositions that it sought to address throughout its term:

First, there was a wider crisis of innovation in the pharmaceutical industry, and the history which we intended to study was one that was emmeshed within a backdrop of reorganizations in industrial R&D of drugs. Strategic decisions with regards to drug development seemed to be moving from labs to marketing departments and board rooms. There was a lament about this in the early 2000s and it was not limited to antibiotics (Braun and Kleinschmidt 2015a; Gaudillière and Thoms 2015; Gaudilliere, Jean-Paul 2021).

Second, we were critical of the notion of our pipeline being propelled by single, genial, and usually male inventors. This had always been a misconception. We decided to look at the pipeline as a community with a gendered structure of people, aims, and objectives (Ortiz-Gomez and Santesmases 2014).

Third, we contended that the notion of an empty pipeline was connected to a traditional overemphasis on biomedical solutions in public health and medicine. The empty pipeline, in that sense, replaced an older antibiotic utopia of a world without infectious disease with a dystopia. Now the absence of new pills is what matters, perpetuating a fixation on technology that had already characterized earlier phases of the antibiotic era (Lie and Podolsky 2016) and that mirrors the broader pharmaceuticalization of global health since the 1980s (João Biehl 2007; Baxerres and Cassier 2022).³

Fourth, a geographical shift in drug production around 1990 appears to be significant. We did not study this, but it was very relevant as a landscape of the geopolitics of the pharmaceutical industry, and of industrial production more broadly. The centres of both production and consumption had so far been in high-income countries in central Europe, Japan, and North America. However, this arrangement sundered: antibiotic production moved to the East, growing markets were increasingly found in the South, and the North continued to dominate intellectual property and the normative sphere by providing guidance and authority on antibiotics use (stewardship) (Klein et al. 2018; Gradmann and Kirchhelle 2023).

Fifth, and connected with the fourth, despite antibiotics molecular innovation is regarded as an ongoing crisis (Silver 2011), antibiotics production, market and consumption still flourish. In the period of our study, it became a bulk market in which generics dominate, although these

² On the history of antibiotics, (Bud 2007; Greenwood 2008; Kirchhelle 2020; Santesmases 2018) can serve as introductions. A good overview over successive generations of drugs can be found in (Greenwood 2008).

³ For an artistic approach to a dystopian post-antibiotic age, see the graphic novel (Kinney and Watkiss 2017).

too might be under pressure (Greene 2014). While the decreasing benefits of antibiotic firms would be an agent in this historization, both this and the bulk market lay outside of the scope of this project.

Sixth, when doomsday prophecies around the lack of antibiotics abounded in the 1990s, opportunities for AMR governance and geopolitics arose. Known results were the EU's 1998 policy framework to confront AMR, the establishment of surveillance networks in the US and EU, the first WHO Global Strategy for Containment of Antimicrobial Resistance (WHO 2001), and the 2015 Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (WHO 2015).

Finally, the rise of new venture-capital based business models from the late 1980s onwards deserved intensive study: the closing down of departments of anti-infectious drug research in pharmaceutical companies happened against the backdrop of pharmaceutical companies' outsourcing of molecular drug innovation to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), giving rise to small biotech companies, working for big pharmaceutical firms and providing new molecules to them (Barrett 2005; O'Neil 2014).

This set of assumptions led to a hypothesis of how things went. In 2021, our initial hypothesis was that the decline, or demise, of antimicrobial R&D happened in three consecutive but distinct waves.

Around 1980, large-scale pharmaceutical chemical or biological screening that had been the dominant model of drug development for decades, went into a crisis: according to what was argued by pharmaceutical companies, screening programs were costly, and benefits no longer seemed to justify those research costs. Increasing benefits was a result taken for granted for owners and shareholders, and this capitalist imagination seems to have guided the reasoning. Also, the chance-based development of some antibiotics, which did not originate in such programs, raised doubts if costly and comprehensive approaches were also rational ones. The problem was to some degree associated with a contemporary scenario of discovery platforms producing dwindling returns. In other words, even some of the new antibiotics found by industry in the 1970s were, to a large degree, derivatives of older compounds (Silver 2011; Gradmann 2016; Greenwood 2008; Lewis 2013).

During the 1990s, technology seemed to offer a way out. Targeted drug development based on genomic methods appeared as a promising, less wasteful approach. Meanwhile, the automation of both the synthesizing of compounds and of their screening offered expanded capacities at much reduced costs. The outcome was, however, to a substantial degree disappointing due to technical and biological challenges (Projan 2002; Sams-Dodd 2005; Payne et al. 2006; Silver 2011). Following wider industry trajectories, 1990s R&D efforts were increasingly conducted by smaller biotech SMEs developing promising compounds, eventually to be brought out by larger investors (Projan 2003; Simpson 2008; Packard 2016; Skender 2024; Alas Portillo 2025).

The years around 2000 saw a wholesale abandonment of antimicrobial research and development by big pharmaceutical companies such as Bayer, Pfizer, Merck, Glaxo Smith Kline, and AstraZeneca, as they closed down their research departments. Despite new public-private initiatives since ca. 2010, no significant industry reinvestment in antibiotic development has occurred (Skender 2024; Paterson 2025; Wells et al. 2025).

The empty pipeline and the demise of the therapeutic revolution

The technology and the so-called therapeutic revolution were key components of this project. With the latter term denoting a process where (beginning in the 1920s) disease treatment therapies were increasingly pharmacological (Bonah et al. 2009). This dependence on medical cures is what many social scientists refer to as the medicalization or pharmaceuticalization of medicine and public health (Biehl 2006). Examples include insulin and cortisone (Haller 2012), which was followed by betablockers, antidiuretics, synthetic antimicrobials (sulphonamides) – and eventually natural product antibiotics. The development of these drug therapies also led to a period of spectacular growth and molecular innovation within the pharmaceutical industry (Greenwood 2008). The core model of how it was done was usually the translation of public funded research and laboratory knowledge into private industrial systems (Mazzucato 2011; Mazzucato and Li 2021).

However, this period of therapeutic revolution and the gradual decline of its promises on the disappearance of infections and the cure of other diseases during the post-war decades was shaped by uneven commercial and scientific attention for different disease classes that were initially identified as belonging to high-income country epidemiologies (Greene 2008). Despite remaining a major global killer, tuberculosis, for example, experienced a rise and fall of attention and investment before eventually becoming a neglected disease with few companies willing to invest in its treatment (Kehr and Condrau 2016; Gradmann 2022). What is important to remember is the so-called therapeutic revolution also had an end. The utopia of a world health protected by public health and drug therapies turned out to be dystopic in the light of the increasing poverty that capitalism created even in high-income countries (Kehr 2018). Beyond antibiotics, there were two interrelated structural changes that came in the 1980s, concurrent with the second and third waves of the decline of antimicrobial R&D mentioned above. First, the centres of large-scale production of pharmaceutical ingredients and generic medicines moved to Asia. Western pharmaceutical companies began outsourcing to India and China around 1990, due to favourable policy changes in both countries, cheaper labour than high-income countries, as well as poor labour rights and environmental regulations. By the early 2000s, almost all fermentation and production facilities of antibiotic APIs had been moved to China, reflecting the strategic reorientation of Western pharmaceutical companies (Zhang and Bjerke 2023; Zhang 2023). Second, and to a large extent as a result of the first, generic medicines became dominant in the markets as production costs were significantly reduced by Asian producers due to cheap labour cost, economics of scale, and patent expiration.

Looking at the tides that were turning in the 1980s, and thinking of antibiotics, we realize how short the therapeutic revolution was – 40 years – a relatively brief episode in the history of contemporary medicine. If it was a revolution, its consequences on the public and medical perception of cure remains, based on a deep faith in medicine and progress even if new social critical movements also arose, as the discussions of this roundtable shows. Interestingly, empty innovation pipelines were not always causes of lamentation. From the late 19th century onwards, the “revolution” of modern microbiology seemed to promise an age of spectacular conquest of infectious disease, yet actual treatments were very slow to emerge. This did not mean that for contemporaries innovation was in a crisis. The instance that it took more than 50 years from the discovery of the *tubercle bacillus* to the discovery of an effective antibiotic, did not fundamentally undermine the contemporaries’ belief in the possibility of antimicrobials. Instead, they continued to believe in its prospects as they believed in science and the laboratory

as engines for progress and cure, as public and private funding does. By the 1930s, synthetic sulphonamides emerged on the market, and the possibility of a systematised innovation pipeline for microbial infections seemed to become a reality (Lesch 2007). This, however, did not mean that industry was optimistic about resulting market success. Shortly before WWII the Bayer company considered developing a medicine for tuberculosis but abandoned the project due to beliefs that targeting a vanishing market as a result of the parallel success of improved public health was not a good idea (Gradmann 2016). Screening methods in pharmaceutical firms' research laboratories remained, as was the case of Merck and some other US firms (Silver 2012; M. Santesmases 2016).

In the case of tuberculosis, powerful new antimicrobial treatments had emerged in the form of streptomycin and isoniazid. The experience of these medicines fuelled the whole industrial-medical system with hopes to cures for other infections. The approach was not without consequences as the case fosfomycin for urinary infections illustrates. (Gómez Rodríguez and Santemases 2025; Alas Portillo 2025). However, by the 1970s, many companies began to abandon clinical and in-vitro testing of potential new treatments. The reason, again, was a combination of marketing research and shifting epidemiology: those who could afford new medicines for tuberculosis, did not need them and those who needed them, could not afford them. In a noteworthy concurrence of evaluations between health policy and industrial strategy in the 1970s, both the WHO and Big Pharma considered tuberculosis to be a management problem that could and would be handled on the basis of the existing pharmacopeia, in other word, generic drugs (Gradmann 2016; McMillen 2015).

This hesitant embrace of sustained antimicrobial innovation was replicated for other bacterial infections, with some companies already reconsidering antimicrobial screening for other infections by the 1950s and some physicians calling for less antibiotics to be developed and an increase of stewardship methods instead (Podolsky 2015). Generic drugs were considered sufficient. For a while, the antibiotic pipeline seemed overburdened with effective yet unprofitable compounds rather than empty (Podolsky 2018; Alas Portillo, Paterson, et al. 2024). This reveals the inherent contradiction of antibiotics as pharmaceutical commodities and the predicament of the pipeline: on the one hand, pharmaceutical companies require economies of scale to remain profitable; on the other, the use of antibiotics must be strictly curtailed.

The emergence of antimicrobial resistance played an important role in shaping both industry and public health policies, leading to an increased interest in systematised antibiotic innovation. This occurred amidst controversies about nontherapeutic antibiotic applications in animal husbandry, antibiotic overprescription for self-limiting infections, and antibiotics' use as efficiency enhancers in health care (MacFarlane and Worboys 2008; Rafferty, Dupree, and Alberti 2021; Kirchhelle 2018). AMR gave rise to a commercial innovation strategy based on targeting the problems created by previous ones (McKenna 2010). In Bayer's case, AMR became an entry into the biological antibiotics market. Discovering drug resistant TB as a new market, the company became a pioneer of combination chemotherapy for tuberculosis in the 1950s. Later on, Bayer followed a product development and marketing strategy that was inspired by targeting strains resistant to older antibiotics. In retrospect this delayed but did not reverse a decision reached in the early 2000s to abandon anti-infective drug development all together (Gradmann 2016; Skender 2024).

Conclusion

Laments about antibiotic innovation have circulated for decades but did little to change the ongoing decline of antibiotic drug development. Should we just disregard them? We should not, because complaints as such also tell a story. To the historian, the ongoing lament about too little or too much innovation on the anti-infective market is connected to contemporaries' dawning realisation of a deeper underlying problem: a sinking feeling that the technological optimism that antibiotics had so much embodied, was going into its eclipse. A mindset, in which modern societies could innovate themselves out of any problem, was losing plausibility when, in the face of AMR, biology and history became closer entangled than they had been before (Landecker 2015). The sad song of empty pipelines, we think, beyond describing an innovation crisis in pharmaceutical industries, is also an attempt to avoid the insight that by the 1980s our use of antibiotics had become unsustainable. The empty pipeline lament, to connect to the title of our meeting, is also a pipedream suited to avoid such inconvenient truths.

This roundtable discussion highlights the experience of those who are continuing to work through the present-day antibiotic development situation and the many points of conflicts and confusion that have stymied further research and success. The participants gathered for this discussion provide, also, their own reflections and concerns as those who are currently managing the aftermath of the historical crises described above and researched through the course of this Dry AP project. And together, they provide a current understanding of what the state of the antibiotic pipeline is and where, perhaps, it might go.

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Round tables with stakeholders - Speaker Key

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CK	Claas Kirchhelle	INSERM Associate Research Professor (Chargé de Recherche), Unité CERMES3, École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales (EHESS)/Université Paris Cité, Principal Investigator Dry AP Project.
ECM	Emilia Cercenado Mansilla	Associate Professor at University Complutense, Madrid. Academic researcher, Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón, Madrid; member of the Scientific Advisory Group of the European Medicines Agency
ELP	Erin L. Paterson	PhD Researcher, Université de Strasbourg, member of Dry AP Project.
FV	Frédéric Vagneron	Associate Professor (Maître de conférences) at Université de Strasbourg, Principal Investigator Dry AP Project.
JH	Jakob Haaber	VP of CRISPR and Delivery Technology at SNIPR BIOME
JL	Jørgen J. Leisner	Associate Professor, Section of, Veterinary Clinical Microbiology, at University of Copenhagen, Principle Investigator Dry AP Project.
KO	Kevin Outtersen	Executive Director of CARB-X, Austin B. Fletcher Professor at Boston University School of Law, partner in DRIVE-AB.
MAP	Mirza Alas Portillo	PhD Researcher, University College of Dublin, member of Dry AP Project.
MJS	María Jesús Santesmases	Research professor, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) at the Institute of Philosophy, Madrid; Principle Investigator of Dry AP Project
MS	Martin Springsklee	Head, Medical Affairs Anti-Infectives, Bayer AG
NW	Nadya Wells	PhD candidate at University of Geneva, Senior Research Adviser, Global Health Centre Geneva Graduate Institute, member of SNF FINPHARM Project.
OG	Olga Genilloud	Scientific Director of Fundación MEDINA, Granada, and Area Head, Microbiology
SE	Suzanne Edwards	Economist and Advisor to Global AMR R&D Hub
SS	Sally Sheard	Executive Dean, Institute of Population Health & Andrew Geddes and John Rankin Professor of Modern History at University of Liverpool; health policy analyst and historian with a research focus in the interface between expert advisers and policymakers.

Ist Round table with stakeholders

9:30 - 11:00: Preclinical to Clinical: Making it into Clinical Development

Stakeholders: Emilia Cercenado Mansilla (ECM), Kevin Outterson (KO), Martin Springsklee (MS)

Opening note: María Jesús Santesmases (MJS)

Chair: Belma Skender (BS)

MJS

Thank you very much to the participants in this round table. Many thanks also to my colleagues in the project, those who are local organizers and especially Belma Skender, whose academic expertise greatly contributes to this conference being productive and inspiring.

We are grateful that you have accepted the invitation so we can listen to your expertise for a better understanding of our own research, of a history of antibiotics, which also involves the reconstruction of science and health policies at international, national, and very local levels, in which evaluation of research tests and clinical trials are key agents.

One of the things we have focused on since the beginning of this international project, was the wide set of agents involved and the complex relationships that made up this network of producing, or aspiring to produce, new commodities, those antibiotics that would contribute to facing the challenge created by antimicrobial resistances.

After the rise of the antibiotic era, right after WWII, and the arrival of the early batches of penicillin, Mary Barber detected in the mid-1940s at Hammersmith Hospital in London what is regarded as the first of these events of the action of penicillin being resisted by microbes in patients.⁴ Later, from the 1960s on, Naomi Datta, also at Hammersmith, greatly inspired by and thanks to early Japanese work on these bio-events, established the basis for the study of the mechanism of resistances, as metabolic sets of chemical paths.⁵ Almost 80 years later, the AMR problem has matured, and as part of a mature society, the industry, international organizations, health policies and emergence of the global as a concept are all embodied in the configuration of resistances as a problem, as a crisis and as a challenge.

⁴ María Jesús Santesmases and Isabel M. Gómez Rodríguez, 'Plasmids and Gender: Woman Microbiologists, Clinical Objects and Tools in Research on Antimicrobial Resistance and Genetics, 1960s-1990s', in *New History of Microbes*, ed. C. Gradmann and M. Grote (Pittsburg University Press, In Press). See also Mary Barber, 'Coagulase-positive Staphylococci Resistant to Penicillin', *The Journal of Pathology and Bacteriology* 59, no. 3 (1947): 373–84, <https://doi.org/10.1002/path.1700590304>.

⁵ Santesmases and Gómez Rodríguez, 'Plasmids and Gender: Woman Microbiologists, Clinical Objects and Tools in Research on Antimicrobial Resistance and Genetics, 1960s-1990s'. Datta was able to identify the mechanism of horizontal gene transfer, as exemplified in her article: N. Datta et al., 'Distribution of Genes for Trimethoprim and Gentamicin Resistance in Bacteria and Their Plasmids in a General Hospital', *Journal of General Microbiology* 118, no. 2 (1980): 495–508, <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-118-2-495>. N. Datta, 'Transmissible Drug Resistance in an Epidemic Strain of Salmonella Typhimurium', *The Journal of Hygiene* 60, no. 3 (1962): 301–10, <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022172400020416>.

As of right after WWII, the ideology of European reconstruction was based on the notion that every problem will be solved by research: it all begins in the laboratory. Since then and until today, the research laboratory is the space where everything starts with a proper design of experiments, a good set of tools, a cleaned-up bench and well-trained experts whose results - a new antimicrobial could well be the case - would not only survive an evaluation by peers but would also enter animal bodies and, if successful, clinical settings in order to check how human bodies deal with substances thought of as being therapeutic.⁶

The clinic would check to what extent the laboratory had succeeded in focusing on particular experiments, targets and molecules. From everyday life in the laboratory to international policy-making by agencies in charge of approving new medical drugs, long biographies of medicines show a set of products whose activity in the human metabolism are submitted for evaluations of growing complexity, with long and ever more difficult lists of requirements. Meanwhile the laboratory, with all its technical facilities and its animalarium, also faced the challenge of defining methods and targets, which shifted from bacteria to the bacterial wall and then just to particular molecules, and left the clinic to deal with human bodies. This transition – from particular molecules to the clinic – takes place through animal bodies, living laboratories, whose use has been regulated by ethical norms.⁷

US expert Lynn Silver⁸ wondered whether the research dedicated to finding new antibiotics would go back to the old, post-WWII screening. From Merck to consultancy, Silver crossed the borders that separated the laboratory from clinical trials and back again, in order to think about the strategies that could be developed for what seemed to be the unsuccessful search for new antibiotics: the famous dry pipeline.

All throughout the 1980s and 1990s until the early 21st century, industrial research laboratories shifted their interest from antimicrobials to other diseases, from infections to cancer and cardiovascular diseases, to chronic disorders.⁹ From cells (bacteria or animal cells) to the molecularization of health. DNA and proteins were fully recognized as expert, master molecules whose activity should be either promoted or neutralized, depending on the case.¹⁰ Living beings,

⁶ For anticancer drug interleukin see: Ilana Löwy, *Between Bench and Bedside: Science, Healing, and Interleukin-2 in a Cancer Ward* (Harvard University Press, 1997).

⁷ For the case of mice and cancer, see: Karen Rader, *Making Mice: Standardizing Animals for American Biomedical Research, 1900-1955* (Princeton University Press, 2004). and Jean-Paul Gaudillière, 'Circulating Mice and Viruses: The Jackson Memorial Laboratory, the National Cancer Institute, and the Genetics of Breast Cancer, 1930-1965', in *The Practices of Human Genetics*, ed. Michael Fortun and Everett Mendelsohn (Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1999).

⁸ Lynn L. Silver, 'Challenges of Antibacterial Discovery', *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 24, no. 1 (2011): 71–109, <https://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.00030-10>.

⁹ Jeremy A. Greene, *Prescribing by Numbers: Drugs and the Definition of Disease* (Johns Hopkins University Press, 2008).

¹⁰ Dorothy Nelkin and M. Susan Lindee, *The DNA Mystique, Conversations in Medicine and Society* (University of Michigan Press, 2004), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.6769>.

however, remain composed by complex relationships between molecules in a diversity of interactions that take place inside cells.¹¹ According to what we are finding in this international project on the recent history of antimicrobials, the research community funded by nation-state science policies is at the origin of any new drug, whether or not it finally undergoes clinical testing. Other recycling practices have also undergone evaluation.

Some of the questions at stake have to do with who promotes research and who blazes the trail towards new antimicrobials, and under what circumstances. According to what we are finding, this does not have a straightforward answer in a simple relationship between an industry interested in profits in current neoliberal capitalism and intervention from agencies like the EMA or FDA. International health policies and their relationship with those of the nations involved in their own leadership, even if powerful, are unable to regulate the molecularization of research and the globalization of clinical trials. Experiments indeed travel, as Adriana Petryna warned us,¹² in the global search by human subjects. We expect to reflect on this with you, contributors to this roundtable, so as to promote a dialogue between the recent past—our project—and your expertise, and we hope that together we can discuss spaces of action, in this transition from pre-clinical to clinical. Welcome and many thanks.

BS

Thank you, Maria, for an excellent opening note to our panel discussion, which will be about the preclinical and clinical stages of research and development of antibiotics in different spaces, private and public. Before we start, I would like to give an introduction to the discussion format today.

First, the discussion will focus on the panellists and their experiences and perceptions of the topic. And later there will be time for questions from the audience for about 20 minutes. I think we can start with each of you introducing yourself and briefly providing your professional background, then tell us when and how each of you first became interested in antibiotics, and what sparked your initial motivation to enter the field of antibiotics. I would like to ask Emilia to start first, then we will move to Martin, and then finally Kevin.

ECM

Thank you, Belma. First of all, good morning to everyone. As you probably may know, I belong to the advisory board for antimicrobials at the European Medicines Agency.¹³

¹¹ María Jesús Santesmases and Edna Suárez-Díaz, 'A Cell-Based Epistemology Human Genetics in the Era of Biomedicine', *Historical Studies in the Natural Sciences* 45, no. 1 (2015): 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.1525/hsns.2015.45.1.1>.

¹² Adriana Petryna, *When Experiments Travel: Clinical Trials and the Global Search for Human Subjects* (Princeton University Press, 2009).

¹³ European Medicines Agency, *Annual Report 2022: The European Medicines Agency's Contribution to Science, Medicines and Health in 2022*, Annual Report (European Medicines Agency, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.2809/175386>.

But my main job is as a clinical microbiologist in the infectious diseases department of the university hospital, Gregorio Marañón, in Madrid, Spain. I also teach microbiology and antibiotics at the university.

As you know, the European Medicines Agency was constituted in 2003, because there was a need for regulation of all antibiotics at the European level; because before that, every country in the European Union validated their own antibiotics.¹⁴ So, as an example, one antibiotic could be used in Denmark, but not in Spain.

The European Commission decided to provide a place to validate, analyse, and study all the antibiotics and to register these antibiotics. But, the final registration (the final acceptance of an antibiotic) is not a property of the European Medicines Agency, but a property of the European Commission, after a positive validation of the European Medicines Agency. The European Medicines Agency is a very complicated organization, where there is a main director, administrators, and different committees. There is a committee for human products, for medical human products, for veterinarian products, for paediatrics, and for rare diseases. So, there are many different committees.¹⁵

At the antibiotic part, I work with the Human Committee, and also with the Veterinarian Committee because there are some rules that must be followed by the veterinarians in which the human committee must participate because they need to perform documents in which they say, well, these antibiotics can only be used in humans, not in veterinary. So, we perform from time to time different documents. Now, there is a huge document that we have been preparing for several years in which we say what antibiotics should only be used in human and not be used in animals.

These committees are composed of different specialists working directly for the EMA from the different national agencies in every country. So, when a pharmaceutical company wants to introduce into the market a new antibiotic, they provide a complete dossier about 300-500 pages to the EMA.¹⁶ The Committee for Human Medical Products then decides on two countries who are going in the first stage to evaluate this antibiotic.

¹⁴ The European Parliament and Council published an updated law governing the European Medicines Agency and its obligations in early 2004. Its new code, providing for greater regulatory oversight can be found: Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 Laying down Community Procedures for the Authorisation and Supervision of Medicinal Products for Human and Veterinary Use and Establishing a European Medicines Agency (Text with EEA Relevance), 136 OJ L (2004), <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2004/726/oj>.

¹⁵ European Medicines Agency, 'Organisational Chart', 16 April 2024.

¹⁶ For more information on what this looks like in practice, consult: 'Marketing Authorisation Guidance Documents | European Medicines Agency (EMA)', 1 June 2016, <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/human-regulatory-overview/marketing-authorisation/marketing-authorisation-guidance-documents>.

Two different countries or nations validate it as a rapporteur and co-rapporteur. They make the first analysis of all the documents sent by the pharmaceutical company, and they have a limited time for doing this. It takes about 210 days to complete this document.

So, they analyse all the documents, discuss the first analysis of the rapporteur and the co-rapporteur at the Committee of the Human Products,¹⁷ take part in many different meetings, provide a first validation or evaluation of this summary, and perform a summary and conclusion of that. Then, well, there are also, an infectious disease working party at the EMA, a permanent infectious disease working party. There is also an antimicrobial specialist party at the EMA. They also always participate in the evaluation and answer different questions asked by the rapporteur and the co-rapporteur.

If they have problems and they don't understand what is said in the documents, for example, if they consider that a clinical study was not well-performed or that the documents haven't included the adequate number of patients or patients with specific diseases (for example, if you want to analyse an antibiotic directed to multi-resistant isolates and in this clinical study they haven't included a specific number of patients with this kind of isolates), they say that probably this antibiotic is not going to be accepted. In this case, they call the scientific advisory group.

I belong to this scientific advisory group. And they ask several questions to the scientific advisory group in order to have a second opinion. The scientific advisory group is a permanent group that is renewed every four or eight years. In this group, there are also many experts from all around the world that come when additional information is necessary. For example, I am not an expert in HIV medication. I know it, but I am not a specialist. When a medication against HIV needs to be addressed, we all go to the core committee, and many people from all over the world who are specialists in HIV also come to that meeting. There is a permanent advisory group and also experts in that specific field.

When the Committee of Human Medical Products (CHMP), has a problem, they write to us all the questions and we have to answer all of these questions. The pharmaceutical company is also asked to answer these questions. And we have a meeting together, the pharmaceutical company and the scientific advisory group, when first the pharmaceutical company gives the response to all these questions. Then they leave the room since they are not allowed to stay, while the scientific advisory group makes their own responses to all the questions that have been performed by the CHMP.

¹⁷ European Medicines Agency, 'Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP)', 25 September 2023, <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/committees/committee-medicinal-products-human-use-chmp>.

After our discussion, we call the pharmaceutical company back in and we tell them our conclusions. We either do not accept the pharmaceutical company's responses, or we do agree. The scientific advisory group then writes a document that is sent to the CHMP. In the end, the CHMP will make their decision of accepting or not accepting the newly proposed antibiotics based on the rapporteur and co-rapporteur, the infectious disease working party, the specialists in antimicrobials in general within the EMA, and the comments from the scientific advisory group.

Sometimes we do have additional questions after that, and we ask the company or the scientific advisory group to answer these questions. But after that, the CHMP informs all parties of their acceptance or rejection of the documents, and their final decision is sent to the European Commission who will finally accept or not accept the commercialization of the product.

- BS How and when did you actually enter the field of antibiotics?
- ECM I was interested in antibiotics both during and after my residency in clinical microbiology and infectious diseases.
- BS When was that?
- ECM Thirty years ago or so, and I was working in resistance to antibiotics. I had several grants for doing research projects on that. I had been working in susceptibility testing since the beginning of my career, and have been working in that for many, many years in different fields.
- BS Was it more of an academic interest at that time?
- ECM No, I mean, academic, yes, because I did research at the university, research at the hospital evaluating antibiotics in vitro activity of antibiotics and looking for mechanisms of resistance to different antibiotics – all kinds of setting breakpoints for some antibiotics. Now the EUCAST¹⁸ is responsible for setting the breakpoints of the antibiotics, but at the beginning it was not that way. Different people were involved in the process.¹⁹ My work is mainly clinical. I mainly work with reading about 300 antibiograms per day, evaluating many different antibiotics and different bacteria in the hospital, and deciding which antibiotics should be given to the specific patients, and then also teaching at the university.
- MS I think you see another living person of history here, because I've been in this field for many years. I will start with the beginning. What actually encouraged my interest into infectious disease treatment was

¹⁸ European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

¹⁹ EUCAST, 'Clinical Breakpoint Tables', accessed 5 June 2026, <https://www.eucast.org/bacteria/clinical-breakpoints-and-interpretation/clinical-breakpoint-tables/>.

one of my early internships in paediatric oncology in the late 80s. And we lost children that otherwise could have survived because even back then with AML²⁰ or ALL²¹ there were some protocols, you know, providing cure rates and we lost children to infections after bone marrow transplants and all these very difficult situations. So that sparked my interest in bacteria, viruses, certainly also parasites and all kinds of these nasty organisms who can kill people specifically when they are vulnerable and they shouldn't actually be killed. So that brought me to the other side. I worked in the lab at the University of Tübingen Medical Microbiology, then later was part, back then breakpoint setting still was a national thing, the German DIN committee,²² you know, we did the German breakpoints. And I joined the pharma industry then, so I went to the “dark side”, if you wish. And actually, now I have been since more than 25 years, with Bayer.

And my first job there was to lead the clinical development for moxifloxacin, the fluoroquinolone antibiotic. I worked also with beta-lactamase inhibitors and other things, and then led the antibacterial and antifungal and antiviral development clinical teams of Bayer for a few years. And actually, I must also admit that I became guilty in a way as part of the team who assessed the economic usefulness or the economic attractiveness of different therapeutic areas within Bayer; in a situation where Bayer really was like you always are, short on money, so you have to focus where do you do your research. And Bayer had a huge research facility in Wuppertal at the research centre,²³ and we said it's economically wise to divest that part, and it did not make any more sense for Bayer if you invest one euro or one Deutsche Mark there, and what is the potential gain that you can get? And I think that was not a particular thing for Bayer, but that happened at that time in the early 2000s in many, many other companies in a very similar way. And still today, I think we hear, but also our patients and those at ICUs, doctors who try to save lives when there is antibacterial resistance hitting. We still are in a way sufferers of that situation.

But I think we also are all part of a solution for that. And probably we'll talk about potential solutions for all of these dilemmas which are out there since many, many years. And I think coming back to history, history is always about long periods of time. And I also think here a long period of time is probably longer than one lifetime of a human. Then it becomes historic in a true sense. And I think we are in that sense, we are responsible for the next history, hopefully to happen, but we are also victims of history we created ourselves in one way or the other, and I think with that I would like to conclude for now.

²⁰ Acute Myeloid Leukaemia (AML)

²¹ Acute Lymphoblastic Leukaemia (ALL)

²² Deutsches Institut für Normung (DIN) – a not-for-profit standardization organization headquartered in Berlin and responsible for maintaining standards throughout various areas of technology.

²³ Bayer Global, ‘Standort Wuppertal’, 20 May 2025, <https://www.bayer.com/de/de/wuppertal-startseite>.

BS Kevin, can you continue with when and how?

KO So I'm a law professor, and that makes me unusual. When I became a professor, the first topic I took up was really global access to drug innovation in the developing world. And I worked a lot with people like Jamie Love²⁴ and MSF²⁵ and whatnot, looking at the ways how intellectual property law doesn't work well for global health innovation outside of high-income countries. Just the discontinuities and the difficulties and problems. But as I was finishing a large article—lawyers like to write large articles that nobody reads—so I was finishing a 68-page article that was published in one of the Yale journals and it was a theoretical examination of everything that works and doesn't work well in pharmaceutical intellectual property law.²⁶

But I recognized that one of the key assumptions behind intellectual property theory would not be true if the drug involved lost effectiveness over time, because the key assumption is that the drug after 15 or 20 years reaches the public domain and is just as good as it ever was. And so, yes, the public has to wait for 20 years—the patent period, but at least they get something useful that would not have been invented otherwise at the end. But that would not be true if, during that intervening time, the product became less effective. And the example I dropped in the footnote²⁷ was antibiotics or anything else for which resistance degrades the effectiveness of the innovation over time, all of the theory that I just summarized would be at risk. So, I couldn't pass that up because it opened up the idea that perhaps everything was upside down when it came to antibacterial and antimicrobial innovation. And that led me to be increasingly obsessed with writing in that area. And it's consumed my life for the past several decades as a result.

I predicted early on that the reimbursement systems—how drugs are paid for—that worked really well or maybe too well in cancer and other fields, would actually have the opposite effect in antibacterials because we want to put the most innovative antibiotic on the shelf to save, reserve and to not use it, which is great for public health, but terrible for the company that brought it to the market. And then I watched as companies like Bayer, Eli Lilly and Novartis and many others went for the exits as a result of that economic analysis.

So, I wish that my academic work had been proven wrong. It actually turned out to be as bad or worse than I predicted. I also like solutions.

²⁴ For a brief biography of Jamie Love, consult: 'James Love', *Knowledge Ecology International*, n.d., accessed 5 June 2026, <https://www.keionline.org/jamie>.

²⁵ Médecins Sans Frontières

²⁶ Aaron S. Kesselheim and Kevin Outterson, 'Improving Antibiotic Markets for Long Term Sustainability', SSRN Scholarly Paper no. 1716942 (Social Science Research Network, 29 November 2010), <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1716942>.

²⁷ Kevin Outterson, 'Pharmaceutical Arbitrage: Balancing Access and Innovation in International Prescription Drug Markets', *Yale Journal of Health Policy, Law & Ethics* 5, no. 1 (2005): 193–291.

In 2015, there was a move afoot leading up to the 2016 high-level meeting of the United Nations²⁸ to think about ways that countries could respond, and this is the genesis of national action plans. The U.S. national action plan called for an accelerator, something that would work with the preclinical pipeline and make sure that we had adequate, highly innovative things that addressed actual human clinical needs, given the economic conditions that I and many others have described in the literature.²⁹ So that was announced in 2016.

Being a U.S. government-started project, there was a public tender, and anyone could apply. I convinced Wellcome Trust to go in as a partnership. The U.S. government originally thought they would do it alone. I said, we should do this as part of a global partnership. Wellcome was the first partner. We added now six out of the seven G7 countries, who fund CARB-X along with three foundations, Wellcome, Gates, and the Nova Nordisk Foundation.³⁰

We are an entirely non-profit. We take no money ever from industry. We are a virtual organization. Two-thirds of our last hiring has been in Europe. Even though I still live in Boston, there is no office anymore post-pandemic. We hold in our hands the preclinical pipeline of the world. I think we support more preclinical work than any large pharma [company] in antibacterials, and I think the last time we checked, CARB-X supports more than all large pharma combined. Maybe you can correct me if I'm wrong on that, but I think that's right.

MS No, no, that's true.

KS Three dozen projects at a time. We're about to add another dozen projects, so we'll be up to in the 40s. One thing I can tell you about the preclinical pipeline of the world is that all the bad news that the WHO says about the advanced clinical pipeline, the Phase 2, 3, is not true in the early stages. The basic research funders of the world, so in the US NIH, and the research foundations and government funders in Europe and the rest of the world have done a good job. There are amazing new classes of drugs. We've supported 35 projects that are first in class small molecule therapeutics plus two dozen projects that are completely novel, non-traditional alternatives to therapeutic antibiotics.³¹ There's a lot of innovation out there. The science is good. The economics are terrible. And I don't know. I think I'll stop there to give you time to ask questions.

²⁸ 'High-Level Meeting on Antimicrobial Resistance', *General Assembly of the United Nations*, n.d., accessed 5 June 2026, <https://www.un.org/pga/71/event-latest/high-level-meeting-on-antimicrobial-resistance/>.

²⁹ The White House, 'National Action Plan for Combating Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria', Washington D.C., March 2015, https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/docs/national_action_plan_for_combating_antibiotic-resistant_bacteria.pdf.

³⁰ CARB-X, *Funding Partners*, n.d., accessed 5 June 2026, <https://carb-x.org/partners/funding-partners/>.

³¹ CARB-X, 'CARB-X Graduates', accessed 5 June 2026, <https://carb-x.org/portfolio/carb-x-graduates/>.

- BS Yeah, so given your different backgrounds and where you worked and from where you come from, can each of you reflect on how the state of antibiotic research and development changed in your area? In the hospital, in an industry company, or in an organization such as CARB-X? Could any of you reflect from your point of view, how that evolved, research and development, preclinical and clinical stages?
- ECM From the clinical point of view, at least what I know from my experience in Spain—though many countries in Europe do the same, all huge hospitals ask us to perform in vitro studies of new molecules.
- We perform in vitro studies with different collections of thousands of organisms with different mechanisms of resistance to different antibiotics. And we perform these in vitro clinical studies because we have a huge collection. They [the hospitals] asked to do that. Also, we take part in some randomized double-blind clinical studies, doing all the susceptibility testing of all studies.
- BS So that was over the time, so when you started it was the same?
- ECM It was the same, yes. Because first in the preclinical stage we have the collection of isolates and we perform the in vitro studies. Then, after we have enough information for that, the company starts asking several hospitals to participate in randomized clinical studies and we participate in different clinical studies with different kinds of drugs. The clinical microbiology laboratory performs all the susceptibility testing of all these isolates and the clinical studies go through the clinical part including patients, etc. And also, all the results of the susceptibility testing of the isolates are sent to a central laboratory in charge of analysing everything. The isolates that we have performed in susceptibility testing are sent to be double-checked in a central laboratory for all the participating hospitals in the world to analyse all these in vitro studies.
- In addition, we have collections of microorganisms with different mechanisms of resistance. So, we include these different types of organisms, species, genera, gram-positive, gram-negative, everything with different mechanisms of resistance. And, if in the clinical study we found an isolate that is resistant to the new drug, we also analyse the mechanism of the resistance to this antibiotic.
- BS So, do I understand it correctly that from the early 1990s, let's say, the processes of how to work with drugs from the laboratory to the clinical haven't changed in Spain?
- ECM No, it hasn't changed but at the beginning we didn't do anything.
- BS I was wondering about that, because I expected in the early 1990s that the processes were different.

- ECM It depended on the hospital, because not all hospitals participated in these processes. For 30 years, before the EMA,³² we did participate in these in vitro studies in our case, but now the participation is more intense. We do more research; we do more everything. But in fact, the participation started before the 1990s. I remember when I was a resident doing in vitro studies for a new drug with the name XAW2234. I didn't know what was that.
- BS So, it was given to you by the company to test in collaboration?
- ECM Yes. The antimicrobial was given to several centres for testing with collections of different microorganisms, and the centres could also present the in vitro results at different meetings or publish them in scientific journals. I think it was very good.
- BS And then you would give the results back to the company?
- ECM Yes.
- BS Martin, can you reflect about that in the industry and in Germany? From the beginning, how did that change over time?
- MS Not so much about Germany, because bacteria and resistance doesn't know any nationalities, so I think it's a global thing, first and foremost. But I think what Emilia was just describing is this very traditional pathway, which was founded more than 120 years ago. The scientific and the technological foundation was laid more than 120 years ago. Robert Koch, Paul Ehrlich and the likes. And we are still struck today with all this innovation, more or less with technologies that are over 100 years old and that's part of the dilemma. It starts with non-traditional approaches to influence the bad things bacteria are doing to the body, which all the agar plate-based technologies won't help at all.
- I think also on the diagnostic side: we are relying on diagnostic technologies that may take days before an outcome is there. How would you ever run the clinical trials? Because you have to include all kinds of patients in whom you hope, for that matter, that a resistant pathogen may eventually show up. And this, of course, illustrates the big dilemma about not only very high regulatory hurdles—you heard about this, the regulatory hurdles for a new drug are almost insurmountable these days, but also the need for investing hundreds of millions in clinical Phase 3 trials, because you need to find a patient. I always kid it, my last sentence is, the best thing to get rid of resistance is if at a clinic, if you run a randomized controlled clinical trial there, then all of a sudden all the resistance magically seems to go away. So, I

³² Known as the European Medicines Evaluation Agency (EMEA) from 1995 to 2003, the European Medicine Agency was renamed as EMA in 2004. Boris Hauray and Philippe Urfalino, 'Mutual Transformation and the Development of European Policy Spaces. The Case of Medicines Licensing', *Journal of European Public Policy* 16, no. 3 (2009): 431–49, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501760802662714>.

think it illustrates the dilemma that we are still struck with very old-fashioned, in my view, outdated technologies which are still regarded as state-of-the-art or gold standards, which won't suffice the new ways that we have to follow, the new path that we will have to follow to make innovation really happen. I think for me that's a big dilemma that we are dealing with.

BS Maybe just an additional question: considering that you come from Bayer—the industry, I'm interested in how processes have changed within the company when a drug goes from research to development. I ask this because you mentioned that you were involved in this process from the early 90s. So, from the early 1990s to, let's say, mid-2000, 2005. So, are you saying that these processes haven't changed or haven't been influenced by external realities or internal factors within the company?

MS It is about to start, hopefully, by the pressure from the preclinical pipeline that is out there right now. And just another remark, I mean, all the big companies, all big pharma walked more or less away early 2000, late 90s. Now we are in 2025. So, we have a time of 25 years that it took to come up with substantial new innovation. So, coming back to the historic aspect, this just tells you how long systems need to react to, let's say, disruptions.

And you can only hope that over the next 25 years, some kind of a critical mass will be achieved. But I think all these megatrends need to be also taken into account when you look at the need for investments, because it's not just one billion or two billion, it's probably 20 billion that you would overall need to pour into the field. And you need to rebuild expertise, create and maintain job opportunities for experts in the field. Be it Bayer, be it other big pharma that had stepped out, the experts had left the companies, and they will never come back unless one re-creates a work environment that attracts expertise with a mid- to long-term perspective.³³³⁴

Once you lost that critical mass as a company or as a research site, it's very hard to bring it back. It may take another generation of highly motivated young scientists to grow up again and to wish to move into that field because there is a career path in front of them.

And all these aspects we need to take into account when we look at how the model got broken and how to fix it.

BS Could [you] elaborate more on your experience at Bayer for the process of moving drugs from preclinical to clinical?

³³ Mirza Alas Portillo et al., *Emerging Financial Models for Antibiotic Development (2000-2016)*, DryAP and Geneva Graduate Institute Witness Seminar (2024), <https://doi.org/10.34931/n7pk-3n88>.

³⁴ AMR Industry Alliance, 'Leaving the Lab: Tracking the Decline in AMR R&D Professionals', Geneva, Switzerland, February 2024, https://www.amrindustryalliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Leaving-the-Lab_final-1.pdf.

MS These criteria are the same of course. You look of course at the in vitro and in vivo models because the good thing is with many traditional antibacterials that you have a high predictive value of these non-clinical tests, which I think is a good thing on one hand. It doesn't work when you go beyond this border of traditional technology. You don't know the predictive value of that.

And, of course, it's toxicology, it's pharmacology, it's pretty simple things like solubility, whether it is orally bioavailable, all these things. There are a lot of technical hurdles also from an API,³⁵ from an active pharmaceutical ingredient to come to a real drug that actually gets distributed in the body. And you can predict all these things quite well with animal and also in vitro cell models, also toxicology. But it is an array of several hurdles that you have to overcome before you can do a first in man.

BS In the 1990s, would you say that these processes were in parallel or they were subsequent?

MS No, we tried to, because time is of the essence: you have your patent life and your development time. And your commercial model only works over the difference between the development time and overall patent life because the patent comes early on. So, in the end you may only get payback time of ten or twelve years, you know? Which is very short, specifically because come back to what Kevin alluded to: these new entities, we should use them the least. And as long as the model is volume, "prescriptions times price makes money," yeah? That model also doesn't really work. So, the hurdles are all there, the technologies to overcome them and to decide "yea" or "nay" for an individual compound or a small molecule or another type of entity are very much the same. They are influenced by the regulatory pathway as well. And all together it amounts to a huge exercise that you have to undertake for a drug that should save lives of a few and not be overused in all those others who don't need it. And that's part of the dilemma as I see it. And sorry to be so negative, but I think by not recognizing and addressing these different hurdles, we are not looking at the whole picture. It's not only the commercial and the financial hurdles that you need to look at.

BS Thank you. Kevin, can you reflect from the mid-2000s, when you entered the field, until now, how the space has evolved, in your opinion?

KO So one thing I want to note in evolution is just what Martin just said about what is typically called "delinkage."³⁶ So let's pay for antibiotics

³⁵ API: Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient(s)

³⁶ For more on the concept of "delinkage," consult: Ellen 't Hoen, 'Innovation and Access Requires "Delinkage"', International Agreements on R&D, *Delinkage*, 13 September 2016, <https://delinkage.org/innovation-access-requires-delinkage/>.

in a radical new way based on value not volume, because paying based on volume makes no sense for these innovative antibiotics.

When I first wrote about that idea in 2003 or 2004, I acknowledged that I got the idea from Jamie Love, the left progressive leader of all things intellectual property in this area, and the companies hated the idea.^{37,38} I worked on it for several years. In 2013, we did a Chatham House series, my co-collaborator at Chatham House was John-Arne Røttingen, who's now the CEO of the Wellcome Trust.³⁹ And at that point, the companies said, "OK, well, maybe this isn't a terrible idea." Five years after that and into today, the companies say, "this is the only way out." There are not many other things in which you could say that the industry has fully embraced a Jamie Love idea.

So, what has changed? A lot of things. I think a major thing that has changed is the industrial and human capital structure of the industry. And Martin already referred to some of this. It is a shrinking, aging workforce. When Novartis quit the field,⁴⁰ I asked Jen Leeds⁴¹ how many people were scientists at Novartis who lost their jobs when they stopped antibiotics. She said over 100.

So, we looked at the eight companies who had announced an exit from antibiotics, including several small companies that had gone bankrupt, and then tracked where their scientists were five years later using LinkedIn. And according to our data set, more than 85% of them had completely left antibiotics within five years, had gone on to other things: immunology was the number one. They just left the field. And a few of them were still in antibiotics and those who were still in antibiotics actually worked for either CARB-X or GARDP. A substantial percentage of the ones left were with us. So, we did that work and then there's a report by the industry called *Leaving the Lab*, which came to about the same results with a different data set, with a different group of companies.⁴² It's shrinking and aging. The big conferences that used to happen, just think of the ICAAC conference, went away.⁴³ For the last five years, the biggest conference for antibacterial drug development has been the joint ESCMID, American

³⁷ Outterson, 'Pharmaceutical Arbitrage'.

³⁸ Sarah Boseley, 'Big Pharma's Worst Nightmare', Society, *The Guardian*, 26 January 2016, <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2016/jan/26/big-pharmas-worst-nightmare>.

³⁹ Edited Charles Clift et al., eds, *Towards a New Global Business Model for Antibiotics: Delinking Revenues from Sales* (Chatham House Report, 2015), https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/field/field_document/20151009NewBusinessModelAntibioticsCliftGopinathanMorelOuttersonRottingenSo.pdf.

⁴⁰ Chris Dall, 'Novartis Drops Antibiotic Development Program', CIDRAP, 12 July 2018, <https://www.cidrap.umn.edu/antimicrobial-stewardship/novartis-drops-antibiotic-development-program>.

⁴¹ Jennifer Leeds is a former Novartis executive who now works for GARDP. More information on her can be found on GARDP's corporate website: GARDP, 'Jennifer Leeds', *REVIVE*, n.d., accessed 5 June 2026, <https://revive.gardp.org/jennifer-leeds/>.

⁴² AMR Industry Alliance, 'Leaving the Lab: Tracking the Decline in AMR R&D Professionals'.

⁴³ Paul Sax, 'Looking Back at a Defunct ID Meeting -- and Ahead to a Thriving One', *HIV and ID Observations*, 12 April 2025, <https://blogs.nejm.org/hiv-id-observations/index.php/looking-back-at-a-defunct-id-meeting-and-ahead-to-a-thriving-one/2025/04/11/>.

Society of Microbiology, conference they've all been between the US and Europe. It was held in Porto this year.⁴⁴ They announced at the end of it that they're done. They're giving up.⁴⁵

These are key indicators. The conferences are dying. The people are dying. They're getting older. You go to these meetings, and there's a lot of people with grey hair. There are not that many people without grey hair. And so, the shrinking and aging workforce is a problem. It is a symptom of the economics for a generation. It's not like we need to recruit better. It's that people want something where there's a future.

Second thing that's changed is how many of these companies are micro and very small.

With all of CARB-X's calls for proposals, we never do anything in secret. We have a public call. We announce to the world, anyone can apply. We received 1,500 applications in front of 105 companies. Some of them institutes and universities and whatnot, but 105 product developers. This last round, when we announced, we looked at all the applications that came in.

And the World Health Organization published a pre-clinical pipeline for antibacterials.⁴⁶ Every company known to them, and they put out a call, please tell us every project in the world, and they published it. And this last time that we ran around, 80% of the product developers were not found on the WHO pipeline report. They'll be on the next one because we'll hand the information over, but they were entirely new. Okay, they're spin outs from universities that are new little companies you've never heard of. We've never heard of half of them, never even heard the name of the company, and we are the world's experts in the clinical pipeline, okay?

But let me tell you what these companies are. They are small-medium enterprise, you know, a small enterprise is less than 50 full-time employees. The greater majority of our applicants are micro with 10 or fewer. These are virtual organizations. They do almost no research in-house. They outsource everything. They are great in whatever their technology is, because typically it's the PI or the PI's grad student who takes the company out. They are the world experts in the technology that they have. What they don't know is how to manufacture a product, how to get it licensed, how to do clinical trials, or the animal models

⁴⁴ 'IMMEM XIV', accessed 5 June 2026, <https://www.escmid.org/congress-events/immem-xiv/>.

⁴⁵ Note that since this interview, a group that includes CARB-X, GARDP, and ESCMID created a new conference GAMRIC which was a sold-out success in the fall of 2025. The conference will return next year in Portugal in a much larger venue. Also, AMS and IDSA have launched the IMARI conference to debut in Las Vegas in Jan 2026.

⁴⁶ World Health Organization, 'WHO Antibacterial Preclinical Pipeline Review', August 2024, <https://www.who.int/observatories/global-observatory-on-health-research-and-development/monitoring/who-antibacterial-preclinical-pipeline-review>.

for toxicology. They have no idea on CMC,⁴⁷ on how to manufacture. And you've seen several recent examples of high-profile antibiotics from small companies that get a complete response letter from the USFDA saying, "You've got CMC problems."

CARB-X gives them money, but we are not just the funder. As Wellcome and the governments will tell anyone, they can give money away. We act in an industrial sense as the large pharma partner that these small-medium enterprises don't have anymore. Because 30 years ago with a pre-clinical asset, they would go to the JP Morgan conference in California. And they would have 40 meetings. Maybe in the 80s, how long ago did they have that many meetings for them...

And then they would present their data and they would get advice. The company would say, listen, we'd be interested in talking to you more if you came back with this study or this result. Or can you compare what you've done to this other program? And it's an iterative open process. And then at some point they get licensed.

And there's some money that flows, but they still own the product. But they now develop it jointly with the big company. And the big company knows what it's doing, even though the small company still is running the program. And then at Phase 2, the big company actually acquires it, takes the option, and runs the clinical testing. All of that, I don't know, elder brother - you know? Somebody who knows what they're doing with the later stages? All of that is gone.

Bayer, it's not that they don't want to talk to them anymore, but Bayer doesn't have the people that could talk to them anymore.

MS I'm the last one.

KO The last person, please turn out the lights. Yeah. And so, CARB-X, the reason why we've hired a number of these people who left other companies is because we are one of the few sources now for that sort of advice for these companies. So, the industrial structure is close to collapse.

And one other thing I'll say is, you asked a question about, are things sequential or parallel? And when you have money, they're parallel. That was COVID. We ran everything in parallel. I mean, we built plants before they had human clinical results, right? When the money is scarce, you move to a Gantt chart,⁴⁸ which is sequential. And so, these projects that we picked up when we started, they're 15 years

⁴⁷ Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls (CMC) – product quality control with an emphasis on how a product is made. Similar to Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP), which focuses more on the overall quality of production process.

⁴⁸ A Gantt chart is a bar chart that illustrates project schedules with tasks on one side and time intervals on the other to display the duration of activity.

away on average from approval. And it's getting longer, because with capital scarcity, they go sequential.

BS But then I'll take this question home. From your experience in the company, for example, could you reflect on this in a sense within the company on how these sponsorships or what we call in academia "grants," worked? I mean, during the 1990s and then the mid-2000s in Bayer, would we imagine that back then in Bayer, things were, for instance, in parallel or sequential? So how did projects or different programmes work because there were many like them?

MS We always had to a certain point in time some competing programmes because we didn't know which of the candidates would really make it or fit best. You can afford this if you pour a lot of money into that system and if you have this justified hope that one of these candidates will make it and will be successful in commercial terms. So you work on that educated hope, guess type of thing, and we always produce a probability of technical success which is kind of an assessment by all the various specialties within the company but also with outside help. And eventually you will have to make a decision because it does not make any sense to do for Phase 2 or Phase 3 large studies in parallel anymore but in the early days you do in parallel work at least as long, as Kevin said, as long as there is not an abundance but there is enough money.

BS So is it like that in what we call pre-clinical?

MS Of course, all the pre-clinical stuff, but pre-clinical is more than just antibiograms. It's making sure early on that you have a production process that can be scaled if you need it, and that you have all the production facilities and up and running and ready for Phase 3. When you start Phase 3, you're not picking big money for the clinical trials, but you have already spent a lot of money on a production facility, on a production pathway, which very often gets under-recognized when you look into the overall funding structure. In the good old days or whatever old days, eventually, as Kevin described, the big pharma company would acquire that a promising candidate run the rest of the show basically. Yeah?

Again, I think it's about de-risking. De-risking always takes time. I think that is the essence—that we have to do a useful de-risking, also being cognizant that we lose more time or take more time. So, the whole patent life model anyway, as Kevin pointed out, is not helpful at all for this type of modalities or entities.

But I think big pharma would, if they were to enter again, they would first have to have an economic promise that is plannable. Because in the old days, I went to my board and said: "I have this idea. We have this and this. This is what we know. This is what we don't know. This is how we want to fill up the "don't-know" gaps. And this takes so and so

long. And I need so and so much money from you. Are you willing to give that to me or is there a competing product in another project, in another therapeutic area, which promises double, I go home.” That was the way how it worked.

BS Martin, can you just briefly elaborate, because it was interesting to hear that there was a specific, or that's what I understood, specific process in Bayer to make decision about moving a product from preclinical to clinical. So, it seems like at that point you also have external data maybe from some spaces, but you also need internal. So how is this decision process? What kind of expertise is there on the table? Who is sitting in this table when you are deciding to move on? What are the vulnerable points in this process?

MS In very blunt terms, it's the point in time where science meets economy and commercial. And you have to be able to explain your science in understandable terms. You want to promise something, but not over-promise. And you are competing at a given point in time with other projects which are at the same stage of maturity within a given company. So all these aspects do play a role. And yes, you bring all the data together. And of course, you also very often bring external experts. But the critical mass model in the pharma industry back then was that most of the expertise was internal. And the external data were kind of additive to it.

And then contract research organizations came up. So now most of this is outsourced, but it's still under the responsibility of a knowledgeable person or a bunch of knowledgeable people at the company who can judge whether what they get is good enough or not. Because you have to make that judgment because nobody else can make that judgment for you. You need expertise for that. But I think that's the process: internal expertise, all kinds of data coming from different sources depending on time and money and then eventually science hits or meets economics and then you get a goal and you get another lump sum of money until you get to the next decision point. And you try to do the best you can with the money that you've been given and hopefully you don't burn it. You also have to describe the risks at this point in time because economists, they also need to know about what the risks are for my money. This is like when you invest in a share, you also look at that. Same thing in your private life.

BS I was always fascinated how science is transformed by economics, but this is just a rhetorical question. Please continue.

KO Can I respond or add to that? So, at CARB-X, we explicitly designed our system to mimic the large company. We do everything by milestone-based payments. We don't necessarily give grants; instead we have contracts, where there's a plan of work and a milestone that's clear. When we get close to the milestone, there's an external review board, which, along with our internal people, evaluates whether the

company and project has met the milestone or whether the places where they missed are significant or not. And then we allocate capital to that. Now, we spend about \$100 million a year from our funders in that capital allocation. And it's all dedicated to antibiotics, so we don't have to fight against the cancer people or something else. That's one advantage. Secondly, we're not looking for profit. CARB-X takes zero economic interest in the company. We're trying to maximize global health and actually move the projects forward. We want there to be something available for the world.

But otherwise, we designed it to mimic the industrial structure because it actually works in many other areas of pharma and would work here if there were a market. Last thing I'll say is that the goal of a pull incentive is that the commercial people and companies would know what the smallest revenues would be. And so, it takes the commercial risk off the table and now all the company would have to evaluate the scientific risk, right? And I'm confident that with the commercial risk off the table, with the sufficient pull incentive, at least some companies will come back, not to end-to-end roles, but come into the role of helping companies and then acquiring them for the CMC and advanced technical development programs.

ECM

I don't want to be so pessimistic. Because, first of all, at the EMA there are specific guidelines for evaluating new antimicrobials, less restrictive. Of course, new antibiotics must have efficacy, security, and quality.

And the quality is very important, as you said before, and the production is very important, and it's also a lot of money. But sometimes pharmaceutical companies start doing research that probably are not that necessary. For example, MRSA⁴⁹ is a big problem, but we have a lot of antibiotics for MRSA.

And the mortality of the patients, even with the new antibiotics, is the same. About 14% to 20% of patients infected with MRSA die, even if you apply the best antibiotic. So, there are more fields in which you have also to improve. It's not only necessary to improve antibiotics, we have to improve the way of treatment for the patient and the adequate use of these antibiotics. For example, in other cases, the big problem now are the carbapenemases, the inhibitors of carbapenemases. Those inhibitors of carbapenemases, are combined with an antibiotic that has been previously approved by the EMA⁵⁰. The EMA has already approved all the clinical trials with the old antibiotic, so you don't need to perform again clinical trials you just have to test the in vitro activity of this new inhibitor of beta-lactamases. You can test it even in a computer. You don't need to do laboratory work. So, this is not as expensive as it used to be. You only have to develop several inhibitors

⁴⁹ Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

⁵⁰ European Medicines Agency

with artificial intelligence, then you can do this experiment. It's not that expensive. And also, for example, if one antibiotic in the combination has been approved before, in the early 90s for instance, the EMA accepts this and does not require a new clinical trial. However, if you want to include new antibiotics in paediatrics, you need to have clinical trials again.

But now it's not necessary for many antibiotics. Yes, you need to have a Pharmaceutical Dynamics and Pharmaceutical Kinetics (PDPK) study, with a computer, with mathematical modelling. And with this, an antibiotic could be approved for paediatrics, if previously it has been approved for adults.

BS So does it mean that preclinical testing is now cheaper than it used to be?

ECM Yeah.

BS But the clinical part is more expensive?

ECM Not necessarily, because you don't need to perform now clinical studies in all kinds of infections existed before. For example, cefiderocol, there are only two clinical studies for two different clinical syndromes.

But, this drug has been approved for all kinds of infections with multi-resistant isolates. So, you don't have to perform five clinical trials evaluating the activity in pneumonia, in skin and soft tissue, et cetera, et cetera.

BS What I hear now is that with some types or classes of antibiotics we actually don't need to run all indications. In that sense, then clinical is not that expensive?

KO The FDA and the EMA have more flexibility, but the result then is that you get to market with a drug that's poorly characterized. You don't have enough data on the drug and then doctors don't use it. So, you can get to approval but you can't get to actual revenues. So, it doesn't actually help at the end of the day. But one thing you said that I want to comment on positively is that we've had a lot of gram-positive antibiotics in the last 15 years, and yet there's still mortality. I think sometimes we shouldn't chase the word resistance always. What we actually need are just better antibiotics. And there are classes of which we just need a better antibiotic. They need to work in children. They need to work in different settings. They need fewer side effects.

So, our focus is on reducing mortality and morbidity in people from bacterial disease. That's what we do. And maybe some of that is gained through an antibiotic to which the bacteria are more susceptible, but it could be gained through an antibiotic that just has fewer side effects, that is oral or taken once, or other characteristics.

ECM Innovation is, of course, necessary. But I think that we can better invest in antibiotics for infections or for bacteria for which we don't have alternatives, for example, carbapenemases. There are many inhibitors of beta-lactamases in the pipeline now. But the problem is that sometimes a compound is combined with an antibiotic that is not the best, because this inhibitor belongs to this pharmaceutical company, and the antibiotic that it is combined with, belongs to a different pharmaceutical company. So, the best antibiotic cannot be combined with the best inhibitor because one antibiotic belongs to one company and the other one belongs to another company. This is also a problem for developing new antibiotics. And also, many companies develop antibiotics that are probably not that necessary. In my point of view, one third-generation cephalosporin with a new inhibitor that was recently approved, cefepime with enmetazobactam, is an example.⁵¹ What is the place for this antibiotic? It is a competitor with many antibiotics that we already have. So probably the development of new antibiotics must be in cooperation with the academy, because sometimes they develop things that are not really necessary. Another example is murepavadin. The EMA and the FDA have approved different antibiotics or antivirals that the company does not continue, for example, plazomicin. It has been approved by the FDA and the EMA. But after the approval, this antibiotic is no longer commercialized.⁵²

I think these could be useful antibiotics in many parts of the world. But sometimes I don't know why a company makes a lot of studies in a drug but then never commercializes it. I don't know.

MS It's because the commercial model is not working. A simple answer.

KO I'll say something in defence. So, the studies began 15 years ago before approval. And at that time, all the experts in the room thought we really needed that because they couldn't see what other people were doing in their preclinical. And in the past couple decades, the companies have been strapped for cash and they tended to go for things that were easier, which is why we see so many beta-lactam, beta-lactamase inhibitor combination products. That's a relatively straightforward pathway. You can take an existing beta-lactam that you feel good about the safety profile and sometimes a generic one to avoid the problems you described and then what you have is a new [beta-lactam antibiotic].

So, we need ways to encourage them to be more creative. But all the programs you talked about were already in the clinic when CARB-X

⁵¹ Maneesh Paul-Satyaseela, 'Invention of Enmetazobactam: An Indian Triumph in Antimicrobial Drug Discovery', *ACS Infectious Diseases* 11, no. 1 (2025): 1–3, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsinfecdis.4c00982>.

⁵² Nadya Wells et al., 'Novel Insights from Financial Analysis of the Failure to Commercialise Plazomicin: Implications for the Antibiotic Investment Ecosystem', *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 11, no. 1 (2024): 941, <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03452-0>.

started. So, it took them five or eight years to get out of the clinic into approval. So that's why we focus almost entirely on entirely new classes and new mechanisms of action so that if something comes out of the CARB-X portfolio, it's going to be new.

- ECM We also have the phage therapy.
- KO Exactly
- ECM And we also have the CRISPR⁵³ technology.
- KO I'm sorry, but how many approved phage therapy?
- ECM Well, not yet. This is innovation!
- KO We have funded four, because we wanted to learn something about phage.⁵⁴ And it's a complex. It's a very different regulatory environment and very different production environment.
- MS Everything is different. It's totally new, uncharted paths, basically.
- KO Which increases the risk, because no one knows exactly how the regulatory authorities will respond to phage.
- MS I maybe just can tell a story about, because you said now there are so many MRSA compounds still coming out. In the mid-90s, we also had what we call target profiles, and one was what we call a grain-positive problem solver. So it was a relatively large profile, which had two profiles depending on which type of compounds. They are in a huge program in oxazole compounds, because there was linezolid from Pharmacia and Upjohn, and we won. I don't know how many thousands of candidates, oxazolidinone. I mean, the only oxazolidinone that finally made it was a non-bacterial oxazolidinone named Rivaroxaban (Xarelto), which was an outcome of that huge oxazolidinone program. But eventually, we decided in early 2000 that it was very likely when we come with one of these compounds it would at best be as good as already existing ones or as the other ones that would come before, and there would not be any market. We had a lot of discussion early on internally of how this is such a promising compound, and how we could kill it, and how we won't go further with it. And on the clinical side we said something will be there so that there will probably not be enough space for it anymore once our product was developed. But you know many other companies have different ways of decision making so they continue because you overcome all the hurdles and then you hit the market, like Achaogen. You hit the market with a lot of enthusiasm and in the company of others, but that market

⁵³ Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats, a gene editing technology.

⁵⁴ One recipient of CARB-X funding for phage therapy is SNIPR BIOME which uses the aforementioned CRISPR technology.

model is still not receptive enough. And then if this company loses funding and property, they go bankrupt, period. And that's it.

- KO Achaogen was spending over \$30 million a year just keeping the plant alive. And their first year of sales was \$900,000. So that's why they went bankrupt.⁵⁵
- BS I would like now to open for questions from the audience, please. Maria?
- MJS Thank you very much. It has been really very informative and we have learned a lot. I'm thinking about these new possibilities—bacteriophages could be a case of proper innovation. But there is not a lot of chemistry. And pharma industries used to be focused on this and it's the easiest way for them to work. It's about molecules, not these tiny organisms where these bacteria and viruses are. It is probable like that from the beginning until today, from Bayer and prontosil until today: pharmaceutical companies have been too focused on chemistry, looking for molecules. Chemistry is really the space in which pharma industry is working.
- KO So I disagree. Today, less than half of the revenues of the pharma industry are small molecule chemicals. More than half are large molecule biologics and complex proteins. Full stop. So, the industry has completely embraced the non-small molecule.
- MJS No, I'm not talking about the size of the molecules, but about molecules themselves. Yeah, a big molecule is also...
- KO The big molecules are proteins and biologics and...
- MJS Yeah, I know. Yeah, that's why I'm talking about molecules and not about other entities that could have been involved in these processes you're talking about. Like, I mean, bacteriophages is a good case. And there is a long history of research on bacteriophages here and there more than, I mean, over decades. I don't know, I just want you to say something.
- ECM Before the pandemics, we had several meetings at the EMA regarding phages, the best regulatory way, and the best investment if we wanted to start innovating with bacteriophages.⁵⁶ At that point, I mean, Russia is the country with the most experience in bacteriophages. And many people from Russia came to the EMA to explain how they did it. After that, as far as I know, everything stopped there.

⁵⁵ For more on Achaogen's story, consult: Wells et al., 'Novel Insights from Financial Analysis of the Failure to Commercialise Plazomicin: Implications for the Antibiotic Investment Ecosystem'.

⁵⁶ Laurent Debarbieux et al., 'A Bacteriophage Journey at the European Medicines Agency', *FEMS Microbiology Letters* 363, no. 2 (2016): fnv225, <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnv225>.

In Spain, for example, in our hospital we have treated several infections with bacteriophages because there is a place in Spain, in Valencia, that produces bacteriophages. You send the isolates to them and they try which bacteriophage or group of phages are able to kill this bacterium. So, there are many different countries in the world, even if bacteriophages are not approved, they are using them to treat infections. And we have some experience, not without difficulties, to treat infections in some patients that had been cured, with the addition of bacteriophages. Of course, you cannot use bacteriophages at a single monotherapy. You have to combine these phages with classic antibiotics – not very active, but they have to be there. So even if the regulation of bacteriophages is stopped at the end, I know that Spain is using bacteriophages in specific clinical settings.

But the problem is that you have to find a specific bacteriophage for a specific bacteria causing the infection. And if not a specific bacteriophage, then a complex of different bacteriophages against this specific bacterium. I think it will be very difficult to find this and to produce this at a higher level. But maybe we can have a kind of regulatory process in which these small laboratories, at least at the national level, where we can use these phages in cases of complicated infections. And we have the experience in treating several patients that were almost dying, and they recovered.

- KO Do you have an educated guess on what percentage of serious infections could be treated by phages if everything was great?
- ECM Yeah.
- KO What do you think?
- ECM No. I mean, we have tried this in specific patients, very few patients. It is probably not very interesting for a pharmaceutical company to invest in that. I mean this year, I think we have used bacteriophages for four patients in four hospitals.
- BS As a reflection it could help precision medicine in that case.
- CK Just to comment on the bacteriophage point, I think Europe's been doing that for quite a long time now. I think since the 1950s, France has been treating patients with bacteriophage routinely in university hospitals. They weren't manufactured by the pharmaceutical sector directly, although they were outsourced to Institut Pasteur's (IP) industrial arm in Lyon. So, the Lyon IP was producing bacteriophage until the 1990s.⁵⁷

⁵⁷ Nicolas Benech et al., 'Les virus au service de la santé : les bactériophages', *médecine/sciences* 38, no. 12 (2022): 1043–51, <https://doi.org/10.1051/medsci/2022169>.

The only reason they got shut down was because they were providing the phage at production price to hospitals, and so they weren't generating enough profit internally to compete with other arms of Pasteur, who were also outsourcing large-particle production to Sanofi at this time. So, in many ways, the phage story in France is a story of a market perhaps not valuing service provision to the health system that Pasteur was providing from the 1950s onwards.

We have similar stories at the Queen Astrid Hospital in Belgium,⁵⁸ and now also at Charité in Berlin,⁵⁹ where all of this is part of a health system service that is being performed by academia. Academia is generating income, but I don't think that these income streams would be recognised within the context of conventional industrial marketing strategies. I think phages are there. I mean, they form part of precision therapy or, you know, however you want to call it for long-term patients. But I don't think that the reimbursement models for phages are in any way legible to anything that's been created in the antimicrobial space so far. It doesn't mean that they aren't profitable. They can produce vast savings for healthcare systems. And I think that – listening to the panel – that we don't have broad categories really to conceive of non-traditional antimicrobials within the innovation space yet. I would like to ask a question in this context to Kevin actually, specifically.

Kevin, I was intrigued by your comment that CARB-X is structured almost like a traditional industrial partner. It's non-profit, right? So you provide this big brother advice. But I wonder whether that is in the long term necessarily a sustainable strategy. I mean, it wasn't as though the traditional industrial model didn't also have its problems with perhaps wrong target selection or a narrow selection of targets going forward. So, I wonder how CARB-X wants to integrate things like bacteriophage going forward that don't fit easily within this traditional big brother industrial matrix.

KO

So I think today CARB-X has made the largest investment of anyone in phage. Our priorities are set by our funders, the six governments and three foundations. So, our priorities, target party profiles, and portfolio strategy is set with global health as the priority. One thing, a question back for Claas. What percentage of infections were treated by phage in France in 1950 or 1960? I still think it's probably only a small number of long-term chronic infections. But at its peak in France, did it address 5 or 10 or 20% of the market? Do you know?

⁵⁸ T. Ferry et al., 'Personalized Bacteriophage Therapy to Treat Pandrug-Resistant Spinal Pseudomonas Aeruginosa Infection', *Nature Communications* 13, no. 1 (2022): 4239, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31837-9>.

⁵⁹ Tamta Tkhilaishvili et al., 'Bacteriophage Therapy as a Treatment Option for Complex Cardiovascular Implant Infection: The German Heart Center Berlin Experience', *The Journal of Heart and Lung Transplantation* 41, no. 5 (2022): 551–55, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healun.2022.01.018>.

CK So retrospectively, as a historian, I have to say there are big limits in terms of me assessing overall infection burdens in France in the 50s and 60s. What I can say is that they were producing 100 orders to 150 orders per year, and that was going up steadily in the 70s and 80s with AMR coming there. Antibiotics in France were being used as first-line treatments at the community level, but the phages were being used for the most expensive patients in the healthcare systems, those who were taking up beds and those with chronic infections. So, this is from an High Income Country (HIC) perspective, and this is a HIC market. However, the story of phages would be different if I tell it in an Indian context for example.

This was where phage was seen as the most useful additional toolkit to traditional antimicrobial therapy. So, I think the question of percentage of infections treated might be slightly misleading here because overall the phages were being used to treat those where AMR was creating the greatest burdens in a system where lots of antimicrobials were still available and lots of antimicrobials were still effective.

KO I guess I'm not trying to be misleading. My point is that I don't think anyone thinks that phage will solve 100% of the problem we're in. It has a niche and that niche is largely because of the need to identify the specific pathogen, and not only the pathogen, but its phage susceptibility. Then to go grab the correct phages out of the bank, you need time. The patient needs to not die within the five days it takes. And so, these are chronic infections, not acute infections, which is a significant expensive subset, but is not the majority. So, my view is that phage can address significant human mortality, but that it is in no sense a solution standing alone. It's an incremental 5%, 10%, 20% addition, not an 80% solution.

CK I would agree, and I think most of the phage researchers would agree that they aren't a broad spectrum *ersatz*. And I also think nobody thinks it's desirable to go for broad spectrum anymore anyway, right? I mean, even in the antibiotic space, everybody's going for small molecules that are targeted.

I think in many ways this is a convergent evolution of two spaces in one direction. But again, the question for me is how effective an industrial system that has grown around antimicrobials, traditional chemical antimicrobials produced by biological substances, is in incorporating these lateral forms of innovation. I appreciate that CARB-X is funding a lot of companies and Jakob⁶⁰ [from SNIPR-biome] is in the room too. But I wonder whether more needs to be done to make this legible in a space where entire regulatory systems still revolve around the antibiotics that created the space in the first place.

⁶⁰ Jakob Haaber, participant in roundtable discussion.

CG I have a bit of a complicated question. I teach infectious disease control and global health in a medical school a lot. And with the students, we invariably come to the crossing in the path that you just described: that with antibiotics, there's probably new molecules, but they don't make it to become medicines. And then invariably somebody would say, OK, could we learn something from other types of medicines?

And people then comment that, why is it, and that would be my question to you, that in the last 20 years where we have a meltdown of antibiotic drug development, vaccine development has been so successful and the market has not collapsed. I have some ideas on that, but I would like to hear yours. Is there some inspiration to be gained from how the vaccine market works in terms of how we can bring new molecules?

KO So we've invested \$90 million in antibacterial vaccines since 2017. We're one of the largest players in that space. I think that the antibacterial vaccine market is in trouble in many ways because the companies that we're supporting are not clear where they will get capital for their Phase 2 and Phase 3 trials. The sources of capital are the Wellcome Trust, the Gates Foundation, and a couple of governments. It's difficult. There have been some high-profile technological failures with the staph vaccines, so we're supporting some staph vaccines that are really completely different than the ones that failed before.

We're doing a program for a maternal vaccine for *Klebsiella* to prevent neonatal sepsis in the developed world.⁶¹ This is largely funded by Gates as the indicated partner for Phase 2 and Phase 3 development. GAVI⁶² is open now, GAVI 6.0, to more antibacterial vaccines, but it's hard for them to make a commitment years in advance when the company is entering Phase 2.

So, I disagree with your premise. I think actually the capital sources in Phase 2 and 3 for antibacterial vaccines are thin and we see a need for more engagement and more funding in that space after they graduate from CARB-X.

CG The point that would then be made in the classroom is that the buyers are very different. For vaccines, you market them to states and organizations. With antibiotics you open that market to an ocean of different customers, so to say, and that's why it's so difficult because it's difficult to predict all the different market accidents and stakes. In that sense, it is the political-economic dominance of the buyers that has

⁶¹ CARB-X, *CARB-X Funds University of Maryland to Develop a Vaccine to Prevent Neonatal Sepsis*, 21 May 2024, <https://carb-x.org/carb-x-news/carb-x-funds-university-of-maryland-to-develop-a-vaccine-to-prevent-neonatal-sepsis/>.

⁶² The Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunizations (GAVI)

kept this system alive. And I wonder if that's where the lesson could lie.

MS But, you know, you're talking about vaccines for diseases that threaten huge populations. I mean, we just learned from the COVID crisis that all of a sudden some threat can come around that eventually pulls a lot of forces together that could not be linked before. It's just because the magnitude of the threat is large enough, you know. But when we talk about antibacterial vaccines, it's much smaller markets in the end compared to an anti-flu or RSV⁶³ or these types of preventative vaccines that you will give to a large, large number of potentially exposed people.

ECM And also there is a problem. I have participated in different clinical trials with vaccines against staphylococci and they have not worked well. I mean, they stopped the investment in that because the vaccines didn't work properly since bacteria are completely different from virus and the vaccines didn't work against the bacteria. But we have different points that we can also address beyond the discovery of new antibiotics. We have a lot of things to do in the hospital, for example, hand hygiene and avoiding the spread of resistance with infection control. This is also very important. And there is another field of innovation that is the CRISPR-Cas. The CRISPR-Cas DNA editing has been used in different clinical trials to avoid the dissemination of resistant genes. Because this CRISPR-Cas system is able to delete the resistant genes, so the bacteria without the gene cannot spread resistance. This is another way to avoid the spread of resistance. So, we have to work in different fields: we have to work in the adequate use of antibiotics; we have to work in nosocomial infection; we have to work in hygiene; and we have to work in vaccines for viral diseases.

We have to work in not using antibiotics for viral diseases. If we don't have antibiotics and we are not going to have more antibiotics, we have to work also in other fields to help that. And it is very important. We have to improve hospital staff and general population education on what an antibiotic is.

We need to have other ways. It's very difficult to have new antibiotics, so we have to work in another field to help that.

JH I just wanted to put a few comments to the phage discussion we had before. We (SNIPR BIOME) use bacteria phages as delivery vehicles of our CRISPR system. We're a CRISPR company using phages as delivery vehicles into bacteria. There's a lot of debate around this personalized medicine because phages are very specific, versus off-the-shelf medicine. And I respectfully disagree with phages only being applicable to personalized medicine. I know there's a lot going on in

⁶³ Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV)

just the Ferry lab in France⁶⁴, and the Pirnay lab in Brussels,⁶⁵ and so on. But we're developing broad, well, broad spectrum in that sense that we are targeting what wouldn't be called a biology without phages.⁶⁶

There are several CMC manufacturers. Jafral Biosolutions in Slovenia for example, produces phages in large quantities through clinical trials, IV grade and so on.⁶⁷ I think there are some structures in place for the more traditional way of antibiotic thinking of using phages. And that's the approach that we are taking.

Of course, then, there's still some, to your point, Maria, on the clinical trials and molecules with the phages, because phages are, well, kind of living molecules. At least phages is a completely different study, because they're self-replicating molecules, whether they're living or not. That's a philosophical discussion.

Crucially I think that, we need randomized clinical trials that show the efficacy of phages. And there's been a lot of anecdotal evidence from Georgia, from Russia, from Poland, and tons of case studies. We are right now also treating one patient under expanded access (N=1). To all of these cases, it's good that we need the randomized clinical trials to show the efficacy of phage-based therapies.

There have been a few that have unfortunately been negative, but we hope that more will come and our medicine and others will pave the way for more broadly applicable things.

KO

So yeah, we're big fans of SNIPR BIOME. We think every phage company in the world applied to us and only a few were funded by us. We think highly of your science. I don't want to leave this group with a negative impression or depressed impression.

Our experience of the preclinical pipeline is that the science is amazing. There are a lot of interesting things out there. My experience with regulators is that they will eventually get to the correct spot. They are showing flexibility and asking good questions. My experience with the bigger companies is that they would like for this solution to be fixed. And they're not opposing—they're trying to work with what they have. It's the economics that are blocking a solution here. It's not science. It's the money. I think the science is there. I'm trying to leave us with a positive, optimistic thought.

⁶⁴ Dr. Tristan Ferry represents the leading phage therapy center in Lyon: Infectious and Tropical Diseases Unit, Croix-Rousse Hospital, Hospices Civils de Lyon, Claude Bernard Lyon1 University, Lyon Centre International de Recherche en Infectiologie, CIRI, Inserm U1111, CNRS UMR5308, ENS de Lyon, UCBL1, Lyon, France Centre de Référence des IOA complexes de Lyon (CRIOAc Lyon)

⁶⁵ Jean-Paul Pirnay is the Head of the Laboratory of Molecular and Cellular Technology Queen Astrid Military Hospital

⁶⁶ Explanation added by JH: broad spectrum usually refers to antibiotics that are killing most bacterial genera. a broad spectrum phage cocktail is very narrow compared to antibiotics. We develop broad acting phage cocktails that, for example, target most E. coli but they are still very narrow compared to any other antimicrobial.

⁶⁷ For more information on this lab consult their website: <https://jafral.com/>

- ECM I don't want to be pessimistic about this either. We have antibiotics to treat the most difficult infection, fortunately. Another problem is that the shortage of antibiotics. Now we have the combination of aztreonam-avibactam that is very good for the new emerging carbopenemase resistance that we have coming from Ukraine. But they can't produce this new combination because there is a shortage of aztreonam and all antibiotics that are only produced in one part of the world. We also have to deal with this shortage of production of all antibiotics. Because sometimes combining old antibiotics with new inhibitors will solve the problem. But we have the problem of the shortage of all antibiotics. And this is not expensive. This is a problem of globalization, that this antibiotic is only produced in one part of the world. And this is probably not an economic problem.
- KO It absolutely is.
- ECM But I do not agree that aztreonam should only be produced in one country in the world.
- KO If you want two countries or two plants, you need to pay a little more. It is an economic issue.
- ECM Everything is an economic issue.
- KO If you want to produce it in Europe, it'll cost more. But it's a good idea.
- MS Yeah, I absolutely agree. I mean, all our societies, I always say to people, if you want cheap, cheap, cheap, you get cheap, cheap, cheap. And that means eventually you can end up in a situation of nothing. If our societies have determined that there are certain critical elements - and I mean, you could look at all kinds, in a philosophical way, all kinds of external threats. Putin is a threat, so you produce more weapons. Very expensive, takes a long time. You produce weapons against a threat which is viral infections or against a threat that is bacterial infections. You have to value these weapons or fire extinguishers, whatever you may call this. You have to value them and be willing to pay an adequate price for it. As long as you want cheap, you will get cheap as a society.

2nd Round table with stakeholders

11:20 - 12:50: Valorisation Then and Now: Beyond Market Failure

Stakeholders: Suzanne Edwards (SE), Olga Genilloud (OG), Jakob Haaber (JH)

Opening note: Frédéric Vagneron (FV)

Chairs: Mirza Alas Portillio (MAP), Erin L. Paterson (ELP)

FV

I'm delighted to open the second roundtable, which in many ways started during the first one. We have a variety of speakers from a wide range of backgrounds. We have Suzanne Edwards, scientific program manager and economist by training and currently working for the Global AMR R&D HUB. She participated in the EU Innovative Medicine Initiative DRIVE-AB project and she's a specialist in pharmaceutical innovation and market failure.

Olga Genilloud is the scientific director of the Fundación MEDINA, a non-profit public-private research organization focusing on the research of novel bioactive microbial natural products. And she's been working in the field of microbiology for more than 20 years, both in the academy, in Spain, and in the US, as well as in the pharma sector in Spain.

And Jakob Haaber has a PhD in molecular biology from the Technical University of Denmark and is currently working at SNIPR BIOME, a Danish biotech company specializing in the development of CRISPR-Cas-Arm-5 phage to prevent and treat bacterial infection.

In this second roundtable, we'll be focusing on the challenges currently facing players in the antibiotic development ecosystem, almost 20 years after the emergence of new policies aimed at repairing market failure.

To put it very bluntly, and then I will give the floor to the roundtable, how do we view national and multilateral attempts to refill the dry pipeline? What have been and what are the windows of opportunities that exist? What have been the points of inflection in the policies?

How has the specific market ecosystem of antibiotics, with its many very specific features, been the laboratory for new economic incentives for players in this sector, increasingly dominated by small and medium enterprises, with the rigged role of the big pharmaceutical firms? More generally, how has this sector contributed to debates on the financing of pharmaceutical research and development, symbolized by discussions around a R&D treaty since the early 2000s that continued on until today (as seen with the difficulties around the pandemic treaty).

I would like to maybe also mention someone whose work is closely related to the DryAP project,- that is Nadya Wells. What do the stories of failure to commercialize plazomicin to patients in the US and Achaogen's bankruptcy in 2020 tell us? Is this the end of the models put in place despite the financial support of big players like BARDA in the US? Is it a "necessary" failure to show that innovation support mechanisms work at the very stage of innovation, but still need to be improved and better funded to ensure effective access, even outside of the richest countries? Or is it just "the wrong drug in the wrong place at the wrong time" (as the authors put it)? And could other pull mechanisms avoid these failures by supporting small businesses?

I think I will stop here because we need our experts to speak together, which is the most important,. Thank you.

MAP Taking from the last panel, I see that you were talking very much about the economics and the commercial aspect. Now I'd like to ask our panellists to reflect a little bit more on where we were and where we're at, taking into consideration what you have seen in this space that has changed, what has worked or has not?

OG Thank you so much and it's a pleasure being here today, and to share the experience from the perspective of coordination, as well as someone who worked for a very large company (Merck) within the early discovery stages. I have seen how the field has been going down. We have tried to launch from the perspective of a non-for-profit research organisation, and tried to assemble all the assets and the resources just to manage to fill the pipeline. And we are currently in the early, early stages. We are not even able to enter into what CARB-X is requiring in terms of criteria just to enter the pipeline. We see that there has been a completely fragmented area in a sense that what was performed in the past within a single organization is now spread along different entities: public and private spin-outs from the universities. Most of these small companies, as was already mentioned, lack experience in developing drugs. And that expertise in development, of course, is just decreasing. People are quitting the field.

It's not only just a problem of people moving away, but it is also that no new generation is coming in, willing to learn and to reinvent the wheel. Very often we see that people develop the same things as those developed 20 years ago but try to propose them as an innovation. There's a lot to be learned from the past, also from the mistakes of the past, but we should try not to repeat the same processes again, especially considering that the resources available for investment are very, very limited.⁶⁸

⁶⁸ For additional references and reflections on memory and continuity in this field, consider: Alas Portillo et al., *Emerging Financial Models for Antibiotic Development (2000-2016)*.

And of course, there is a huge effort that is being done by the accelerators. Is this still enough just to fill the pipeline? Because the attrition rates are still there, and the criteria just to manage to get the molecule into a Phase 1 clinic are what they are. These are not going to be decreasing. No matter what innovation that we have, they are going to be facing that. We know the success rate is really, really low. The point is how we can provide for larger molecules to enter the system, while at the same time engaging or having additional accelerators at different levels to get them through.

I have experience from the IMI⁶⁹ program here. We were one of the first projects that were proposed for this purpose. For instance, in ENABLE, we had the experience of gathering companies, private organizations, and academic partners to try to build this pipeline together.⁷⁰ This is probably one of the few accelerators that enables the very, very early parts of the process with the molecule so it can move to a lead. It will then be able to enter into a scheme like CARB-X or another similar approach.

There is a really big gap for the innovation that is being developed in the academic sector, which is more derived from basic research. And grants are not covering that. This is a high-risk area where we can just generate future novelty that will eventually be put into the system and will manage to get through all the existing accelerators that will deliver the clinical candidates.

SE

I think I should probably start with a disclaimer as a consultant. I would try and keep on my global AMR R&D hat, but inevitably it will slip. The Global AMR R&D Hub was formed from the G20 processes back in 2018 when Germany held that presidency.⁷¹ We hold the biggest repository of funding data that is going in public and philanthropic funding. This is obviously a tiny proportion of the investments that are being made into this, but we focus on the public and philanthropic. We have ongoing efforts to try to get venture capitalism and various other very important funding streams, but at the moment, the data set is largely public and philanthropic. Then, we try to pull together across the world all the funding that is going into AMR R&D.

So, it's a shameless plug, right? I'm sure this foundational dataset could potentially be very valuable for much of this work. Unfortunately, it doesn't go back quite as long in history as we would like, starting in about, I think, 2016/2017. What we also do, as well as tracking the investments, is we also try to track the incentives. Starting five years

⁶⁹ Innovative Medicines Initiative

⁷⁰ European Gram Negative AntiBacterial Engine: ENABLE, 'Welcome to ENABLE', 7 March 2023, <https://web.archive.org/web/20230307212920/http://nd4bb-enable.eu/>.

⁷¹ Global AMR R&D Hub, 'History of the Hub', accessed 8 June 2026, <https://globalamrhub.org/history-of-the-hub/>.

ago, we started with looking across the value chain as one of the main funnelling streams and incentives.

In the next couple of weeks, we'll actually be releasing a second visualization of this, which is focusing on the pull incentives.⁷² The hope is to bring more visibility now in this slightly gloom and doom world, because obviously the opening question was really about how we see the changes and the developments in the space? This new tool to track pull incentives separately just wasn't feasible five years ago when we originally built this dashboard. So, I think that is indicative of the broader trends that we probably see, which is: we see great incentives; we see great progress at various points in the value chain where the public is stepping up and the philanthropic organisations are stepping up to address some of the many challenges that have been discussed in the last couple of years. So obviously we've got CARB-X, and there's GARDP. There's a lot of work, I think, perhaps insufficient work, but happening on clinical trials, right? These are conducted in an extremely fragmented and inefficient way in order to gather and generate the data, which is historically extremely difficult clinical data to generate in this space and how to look at greater efficiencies in how we conduct clinical trials. These are all things in the pre-market space. We track this, we see these great developments. About 10 years ago, we saw some steps from the regulators to try to look at their role in this and how they can expedite or reduce the barriers to these products coming to market.⁷³ And then now, obviously, in the post-approval space with the question of reward and valuation, we're starting to see mini steps of progress.

I'd like to draw it back to the point that we keep coming back to, which is that the value chain is a sticking cluster with little bits of technical solution here to fill a gap and address a challenge, right? But what we don't yet have is a coherent ecosystem that's connected and works. One of the questions I wanted to ask earlier is, what happens, Kevin, to your products when the funding stops? What's the next step? Is there a follow up?

There is no coherent pathway for these products in the way that they used to be 50 years ago when this was end-to-end and in-house. I think to sum up what we see, you can take an optimistic approach to this or you can take a more pessimistic angle. We do see these initiatives these PDPs, and this progress from governments, but it's fragmented. It feels like a sticking plaster of solutions for all the many problems along the way.

JH

Thank you. I would like to say first of all, thanks for the invitation to this discussion. I think it's absolutely fantastic to be here. As I was

⁷² Global AMR R&D Hub, 'Global AMR R&D Hub Dashboard', accessed 8 June 2026, <https://dashboard.globalamrhub.org/reports/incentives/incentives>.

⁷³ Comment added by SE: since the meeting there have been big steps via the update to the General Pharmaceutical Legislation

introduced, I'm a microbiologist by training and I'm a scientist. I am heading the research at SNIPR BIOME, and so I'll try to not pretend that I know all these models and initiatives that my co-panellists are much better at, but I will try to give my perspective from a small biotech company that is trying to develop these novel medicines to treat antimicrobial resistant infections.

Instead of going into the past, I think I'll go more into where we are now and try to tell you what we do at SNIPR BIOME, how we are developing these drugs, and how we are then negotiating this financial environment that we are living in. SNIPER BIOME is based in Copenhagen. We are a small biotech company of around 40 people. We're not the micro, but one of the small enterprises Kevin was talking to about before. We develop quite novel technologies and use live bacterial products as our drug entity. We are using CRISPR, as was mentioned before and using either live bacteria or live phages as delivery vehicles to the bacteria that we want to kill with our CRISPR systems.

CRISPR is a molecule which can very precisely cut DNA. And when you cut DNA, bacterial genomes die. We use CRISPR to very specifically target bacteria that we want to kill by delivering a piece of DNA, which is then turned into a protein into the target cell, then cuts the DNA of the target cell and kills it. The beauty of CRISPR is that it is programmable. We can decide where to cut in the bacteria. When we know the bacterial genome, we can actually say we want to cut this E. coli genome, but not that E. coli genome. It's very specific and it's programmable. And that also allows us, to use both the programmable CRISPR system that can easily be changed, as well as phage delivery vehicles that we can also update. We think that we can apply a kind of flu vaccine approach to our technology. So, resistance develops either against phages, or antibiotics, or so on. By not using a small molecule, we believe that we can change either the way that the bacteria feeds, binds to the bacteria or the crystal system, how it cuts and so on, and update our medicines on a flu vaccine kind of basis, at least in the future. I know it's not there yet.

That's what we do. So, what is our path into developing these new novel medicines and how do we try to bring it forward? Because at the end of the day, as you say, we need to get through the clinical testing and actually get access – get it out to the people where it can work. So, I will give you just a very brief history of where we were and where we are now. I think innovation really is very bottom up. These kinds of new technologies, as Kevin was also saying in the last round, really comes as spin-out of universities. The PI or a student gets an idea and it gets spun out. And that was essentially how SNIPR was founded also.

I think it was an interesting combination of our CEO who was a serial entrepreneur, with big pharma experience, biotech experience,

Wellcome Trust and so on. And he, together with a very young, also very entrepreneurial professor from the Technical University of Denmark, who was, very importantly also a very experienced patent lawyer. They started SNIPR BIOME in 2015 when all the CRISPR hype was really high. It was Doudna⁷⁴ and Feng Zhang⁷⁵ and all that huge periodic things with CRISPR. They got the idea, they made some fundamental experiments in the lab, and then they filed a seminal patent that was granted. So, we have a very broad US patent that has allowed us to do what we can do. And I need to stress the importance of that, because that allowed us to even get our seed funding. If we had not had that patent we would not have gotten the seed funding in the first place. Then, with that seed funding, we generated more data and were able to raise the Series A of \$50 million USD in 2019.⁷⁶

So, this was a combination of a large Danish foundation called the Lundbeck Foundation who was our seed funder, and they are also the lead investor in our Series A. And I think that's important because they have long-term horizons, the Lundbeck Foundation.⁷⁷ That means they can see more than two or three years out in the future. We also have ventures as our investors, so I think we have a very strong combination of investors. But that was really because we had IP and then we had this strong investor group.

I think just to round off this part, because now we're in Series B raising⁷⁸ right now, and I just want to say that we have actually an orthogonal technology leg in SNIPR. And that's using live bacteria to produce beneficial molecules *in situ*, in the gut of people. And that allows us to secrete nanobodies and to convert metabolites in the gut. And why I'm telling you this is because that has potential implications or potential medicines for IBD, for type 2 diabetes and so on. So, we have these two legs and it's very interesting now when we're in Series B raise, when we speak to pharma, when we speak to venture, they say, "This is super interesting...by the way, come back when you have the Phase 2 data."

But when we then tell them that we have this very interesting asset that is actually now past the Phase 1A and into a Phase 1B, they say, "But this is AMR."

⁷⁴ Doudna Lab, 'Doudna Lab | RNA Biology at UC Berkeley, HHMI', 3 November 2025, <https://doudnalab.org/>.

⁷⁵ Broad Institute, 'Zhang Lab', 13 June 2016, <https://www.broadinstitute.org/zhang-lab>.

⁷⁶ Nick Paul Taylor, 'Snipr Raises \$50M to Use CRISPR to Modulate the Microbiome', Fierce Biotech, 11 March 2019, <https://www.fiercebiotech.com/biotech/snipr-raises-50m-to-use-crispr-to-modulate-microbiome>.

⁷⁷ Christian Grøndahl, 'SNIPR BIOME Announces Pioneering Work on CRISPR Targeting of Microbiomes Is Recognised as European Patent Office Grants Fundamental Patent Rights', The Lundbeck Foundation, 15 December 2021, <https://lundbeckfonden.com/business-activities/lundbeckfonden-emerge/portfolio/news/snipr-biome-announces-pioneering-work-on>.

⁷⁸ Comment added by JH: Series B raising is the next round of private funding following the Series A at SNIPR BIOME. Consult: <https://www.sniprbiome.com/s/250807-SNIPR-Biome-Series-B-announcement.pdf>.

So, we have four programs in antimicrobial medicines, and they are mostly funded and supported by CARB-X. We have one early project which is funded by the Gates Foundation. We have actually a project based on the technology that was discussed at the previous roundtable, on resynthesizing bacteria by cutting their AMR genes, so you can revitalize the old antibiotics that are not working anymore. And that's together with the German government of Sprung Innovation, the Sprint D, the German governmental institution right under the chancellor of disruptive innovation. And it's just interesting. One of the key points for being eligible for Sprint funding is actually that you have a project that nobody wants to touch because it's not economically viable. So, I think I'll leave it here, but it's just to say that there's a very, very clear distinction between what venture is interested in, what pharma is interested in, and then the AMR problem that we need public and the philanthropic funding for. Thank you.

MAP

I was thinking about what Suzanne was referring about the ecosystems. What would a future ecosystem look like? And also, as Jakob just mentioned, funding for a small company comes from a combination of big public funding, government, and private. Olga also mentioned that funding is fragmented and it's difficult with the grants. If we could reflect, what is a kind of pathway for this very high-risk research? How do you think of communities, or what are the kinds of people you approach to ask for this funding? I would say to especially Suzanne, because you are very much seeing this big picture of the ecosystem and all of these fragments. What would a more ideal system look like? What could be parts of it that maybe we're not seeing or thinking about that could also come in?

JH

I'm more of a scientist but what I can see is that this public and philanthropic funding is absolutely crucial for us to be able to push our medicine forward. I'm curious to hear the other panellists on this, but I think my impression is that if some of these pull incentives, so say there's a voucher, for example, in the EU that will allow you to have a patent extension for one year that you could sell to somebody producing medicine, for example. I think that would worth a lot of money, and that could re-spark the interest from venture, at least. I'm not sure about pharma, but I think that could open up some of the interest so that the venture people could see a way forward for getting a return of the investment.

SE

So, looking into the future. What I rather derogatorily referred to earlier is the "sticking plaster solutions" that we have at the moment in terms of GARDP and CARB-X, right? I think these initiatives and these steps that we're taking are necessary, right?

To take a specific example on the pull side, as we collate the progress on the pull side and try to bring this in a very accessible level to policymakers, what you see increasingly with countries working on this and how they value these products is not necessarily how much

new resource this is going to generate but rather to reward companies that are successful. And Kevin's the person to really give you that assessment of whether the money is going to be enough? Are these valuation mechanisms really going to result in a significant enough pull that will re-spark interest? What's interesting for me about this, is what you see happening in governments in high-income countries. They're actually starting to ask these questions and starting to look into their own systems, right?

I used to do some work on comparative health systems with the European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies.⁷⁹ This plays into the point that has come up so far this morning, which is about fragmentation. So even when a product in this space reaches registration and succeeds registration, we've still heard that it is a very long way away from a patient gaining access to that product. And therefore, that's the point at which the money is generated that goes back further in the system.

There are many, many steps at the national level: as soon as a product hits a country and gets a registration, gets an approval in a country, it then has to find its way through these extremely complicated health systems with multiple requests and levels in them before that sale can be generated. And looking at that pathway is really critical. To take a very concrete example of this from Germany, with regard to bedaquiline.⁸⁰⁸¹ This is a product that is well-priced in Europe. It is also an antibiotic that is highly innovative. This is truly a breakthrough product. This is valued in Germany.

But what happens in reality is this: you've got a multidrug-resistant tuberculosis and you are in a hospital being treated by bedaquiline, but hospitals in Germany at the moment make a loss if they prescribe that product, right? Because of the DRG [Diagnosis Related Groups], the reimbursement package for holistically treating that patient has not adjusted to accommodate the fact that somewhere further up the line, somebody has agreed to pay more money for this product. So, at each step in the process, there are bottlenecks to value realization in very concrete terms. And I think this is the windows of opportunity that we were talking about or this is a development that excites me.

I would hope that after these years, countries will be starting to look into their systems and to ask the question, how is value actually realized for these products within our systems? These are very small, concrete things that I'm quite excited about. The question was actually about imagining what an ideal system would look like. A lot of the

⁷⁹ World Health Organization, 'European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies', accessed 8 June 2026, <https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/home>.

⁸⁰ Rajiv Mahajan, 'Bedaquiline: First FDA-Approved Tuberculosis Drug in 40 Years', *International Journal of Applied and Basic Medical Research* 3, no. 1 (2013): 1, <https://doi.org/10.4103/2229-516X.112228>.

⁸¹ Erin Lindsey Paterson, 'A Crumbling Infrastructure : Questioning the Stability of Access to Antibiotics New and Old' (Université de Strasbourg, 2025).

discussion has obviously been about the crisis of scientific innovation and the crisis of development innovation. I think we need political and policy innovation as well. And I would actually say that is where the real innovation crisis is.

Like Kevin, I've been involved in these discussions since Sweden actually brought this topic to the agenda back in 2009⁸² when I was still a student and working at the London School of Economics. We need bold government. We need bold policymakers that are able to see their systems and are able to understand, as we learned this morning, that the patent system has been a brilliant foundation in general for biomedical innovation but does not serve well in many areas, particularly antibiotics and anti-infectives in general, because of externalities and various other things.

I really value the conversations we've had so far and obviously being around historians and thinking about this concept of how you bring the lessons from the past and relevantly use them and learn from them in the future. And I think we're not doing that well in this space. I'm sympathetic to this. I'm somebody that sits on a huge data set that has to synthesize that into soundbites. And I think this is a challenge for everybody.

But the other thing, as well as the collective history, I think this space is particularly challenged by not learning. And I think this talks to your point that you made this morning. We don't really learn the lessons. We're not really looking outside of our bubble, our silo, and learning the lessons that are abound in other areas such as anti-infections and global health, right?

I think one of the areas that frustrates me the most is infectious diseases. The burden of infectious diseases falls and has always fallen most heavily in low- and middle-income countries. We have two decades of experience now in trying to fix these markets, in trying to overcome some of these challenges on access and so forth, be it the global fund, pool procurement, regulatory strengthening, all of these things. You have 20 years of experience that we're not drawing on in this space to learn those models.

You don't hear about market shaping—the concept of how governments influence how markets work for public health. You don't even hear this language when we're talking about high income countries, right? Let alone sort of learning the tools. Obviously, the UK subscription model is fantastic with its high profile pull incentives, but it's essentially a value guarantee that has been used extensively in other parts of the world with very practical experience for very long.⁸³

⁸² Paterson, 'A Crumbling Infrastructure : Questioning the Stability of Access to Antibiotics New and Old'. 160-163.

⁸³ Rebecca E. Glover et al., 'Why Is the UK Subscription Model for Antibiotics Considered Successful?', *The Lancet. Microbe* 4, no. 11 (2023): e852–53, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(23\)00250-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(23)00250-1).

Tuberculosis is a bit of a pet project of mine, but this is just one example.

OG

Of course, I need to do it from the early stages since that's where we are operating. Of course, for anyone that is just looking into the medium-long term, this is a very complex path. There needs to be some alignment in terms of what the objectives are, how you want to achieve them any time that you have a potential new compound, and which type of application and guidelines. Many people are just entering the field without having any information, not knowing who to contact and where to go just to manage to get this process going. But in any case, there is a lot of ongoing discussion not only in academia but also in the small companies just on engaging with these initial steps.

Globally, there is also movement in terms of how we are going to be funding early discovery and this innovation. Not just the basic research driven by curiosity. It's also very difficult to fund in this specific field. The sources are going to come just to foster on one side of this innovation, but at the same time, how are we going to gather this and to channel that into a new product? That can be small molecules or many other types of modalities that can be applied, and that's proposed just for development in the pipeline.

So, in these stages, we are working at the national level in trying to make them understand there is a big gap in the type of science they are supporting and the basic research that can generate this data. In fact, the basic issues and challenges in antibiotic discovery are still there. Most of them have not been overcome and there's still not enough information. We need to continue to foster this research to manage to get the innovation after that. And this is not sufficiently supported from the different granting institutions.

But at the same time, there is no place in this system to have more high-risk projects where you want to have this proof of concept, or where you want to move ahead from the very basic research to have a project that at the end is ready to start delivering different potential products into the pipeline. There is a lot of discussion and there's been this C4G global initiative that was started one year ago. We also have a guardian board. We have been discussing a lot about how to manage the basic research and innovation in all the academic centres globally, it's not only just Europe, but also centres in the US, in Asia, and in South Africa, to gather resources. But these also need to be granted by charities in a certain way just to foster this initiative in order for it to proceed to the end so that these projects can eventually fill the pipeline.

All these gaps are attempted to be filled by the different communities, but independently from the others. So, there should be some alignment in trying to have general objectives. Where do you want to be in five, or ten years? Because it is going to take a lot of time when you don't

have a streamlined process that is clear for all of the members. How is it going to take place and make the lead to another step? That's probably something that would need to be organized. The job that is being done by the organizations such as trying to put in line what the resources are, or what criteria are needed to enter into the different development programs is crucial just to avoid losing resources and energy into projects that are going nowhere because there is no expertise. Advice given quite early in the process on where to put resources effectively is limited. It's always a question of funding, and no matter in which stage of your process you will need to rely on what is available.

So how can we leverage all the innovation that is ready to be exported and try to go globally in the right direction instead of disperse and dilute the efforts - that's what we are seeing today in the early stages.

JH

On a different note, I just want to address the sense of urgency in the AMR crisis. The AMR crisis and the climate crisis share some of the same problems in that it's a slow creeping problem that is not right now super apparent, at least not in the countries where the money is. When we're trying to design our trials, we face discussions with doctors that say, "you know, the antibiotics still work." Luckily, at least in our part of the world, you can treat most of the infections with the available antibiotics. But what people are not aware of is that it's taking a long time to develop these antibiotics. And I don't know. I'm just thinking if there's something about the awareness of this problem that we can work on.

Because bugs travel, I mean, everybody knows that. If a multi-resistant bacteria is identified, you can follow it around the world. You can follow them within hospitals and so on. I went to the GARDP website to see who are they and who are you and so on. And the first thing that came up was a banner saying, every eight seconds a person is dying from an AMR infection.⁸⁴ And that kind of struck me. I know it's like saying you're putting crisis on top of your agenda. But that's the message that we need to convey somehow to the decision makers that in ten years' time, in order to be able to treat patients in Europe and in the US, we need to start with the whole process now.

SS

So ten years ago I published a biography of a passionate economist, Brian Abel-Smith, who was one of the first health economists to develop a model of health accounts at country level.⁸⁵ And he was an advocate for what you talked about, Suzanne, which is looking at the funding ecosystems. But he also identified and spoke to a growing crisis which was around user fees for healthcare in low- and middle-

⁸⁴ This banner, currently reading "Approximately every 6 seconds, a life is lost to AMR." Is available on the GARDP website as of June 27, 2025: <https://gardp.org/>.

⁸⁵ Sally Sheard, *The Passionate Economist: How Brian Abel-Smith Shaped Global Health and Social Welfare* (Policy Press, 2014).

income countries. He did a lot of work in Sub-Saharan Africa. And he exposed really what the World Bank was doing and the influence of the World Bank on setting the path dependency that I think we're still on. We've not talked at all about the World Bank in this meeting. So I'm just putting that out as another provocation, but why are we not talking about some of those other big players like the World Bank?

NW

I just wanted to briefly mention a paper that we published about Achaogen's demise that Kevin and John Rex have talked about. It was a post mortem. And I just wanted to bring some of the findings into the conversation. We found that 71% of the pathway was driven by private finance.⁸⁶ The SME (small and medium sized companies) dependency of the pipeline is even bigger now than it was then. I listened to all of your comments, of course, and all the critiques, which are all included in the paper, of the incentives that are on the table. But the reality of what we are dependent on for producing what we may need in the future today is that those actors are doing it – people like you are doing it. And it has been hugely dependent on this blended finance model of public and private. And this is a different space from what we normally hear in assets management, which is all about public financing at the beginning and privatisation of profits at the end. There are no profits. As you get to the point of commercialisation, the costs are what you've already spent or more again. And there's no funding for that at the moment.

And that's the moment that you become incredibly reliant on private finance. I think we can't ignore that in this space. And I would just say that if you listen to the panel, you should be happy that ecosystems are the title and market shakings are the conclusions.

SE

I'm definitely talking from a personal perspective now. I think what we see with the World Bank is that some of those traditional global health actors are cautious. This is not just the World Bank, it's also Gates, right?⁸⁷ Sort of on the edge, sometimes producing, sometimes stepping in. This is a difficult issue, not least because neglected tropical diseases are problems over *there*. It's for the poorest and most excluded. We can throw money at that. Nobody's going to question our involvement in supporting something like that. This is in quite contrast to that. This really is a topic that sits in a bit of a void between the GARDP space, the low- and middle-income country space, and the high-income space. And I think there is tension there.

I think I would love to see the blended finance model with neglected tropical diseases. There is a little bit more focus on what models we have used before in neglected tropical diseases, like entirely 100% donor finance or the full private model. It doesn't seem to me that the

⁸⁶ Wells et al., 'Novel Insights from Financial Analysis of the Failure to Commercialise Plazomicin: Implications for the Antibiotic Investment Ecosystem'.

⁸⁷ Alas Portillo et al., *Emerging Financial Models for Antibiotic Development (2000-2016)*. 66-68.

models that we've used in other areas are going to be directly translatable to this. And that's why I think your work is important, particularly critically looking at what new models are or what are blended in models that are neither traditionally not-for-profit nor traditionally 100% for profit. That's where I would love to see this policy innovation.

KO

I think that pull incentives must have conditionalities. That's how I interpreted it. You can tell me if I have the meaning right. We have to have a pull incentive, but there has to be a requirement for global access. Every setting I ever go to, I say it must be as good as the Shinogi license with GARDP or better.⁸⁸ That's the new baseline. And that should be required as a condition of getting a nickel. Similarly, with paediatric studies, it must be a contractual condition of receiving those funds. But on the paediatric, I just want to ask back, I know that in the United States it's been federal law for 20 years requiring paediatric studies. But there have been too many exceptions. And for a long period of time, not quite as long, it's been the law here in Europe. And so, we've tried this. And there have been many critics, including my good friend Aaron Kesselheim who recently published a list of the ways in which all the companies have done it about half the time.⁸⁹ It's not nothing, but it's also not what the governments told them to do. My point there is just that the US and Europe have been fighting this battle with the companies for two decades. And it's an undone job. We have to have realistic understanding of how hard these fights are.

CG

This is becoming a bit of an AMR discussion. We had this comparison on the table about climate change and AMR containment.⁹⁰ I know you have been pretty gloomy around the table here for a couple of hours, but there is something that speaks in favour of handling AMR: and that is that in climate change policies you have a tragedy of the common problem. Anybody can wait for the others to take action. Whoever takes action first ends up with paying most of the bill. As compared to this local action in containing AMR makes sense and works, just look at it and see if you compare it to the epidemiology of Belgium and the Netherlands [where different local policies have translated into very different epidemiologies], and you see what can be done. In that sense,

⁸⁸ GARDP and the pharmaceutical company Shinogi engaged in the licensing of the drug cefiderocol to provide increased access to low income patients in need. For more information, consult: GARDP, 'Shionogi, GARDP and CHAI Announce Landmark License and Collaboration Agreements to Treat Bacterial Infections by Expanding Access to Cefiderocol in 135 Countries', 15 June 2022, <https://gardp.org/shionogi-gardp-and-chai-announce-landmark-license-and-collaboration-agreements-to-treat-bacterial-infections-by-expanding-access-to-cefiderocol-in-135-countries/>.

⁸⁹ Thomas J. Hwang et al., 'Completion Rate and Reporting of Mandatory Pediatric Postmarketing Studies Under the US Pediatric Research Equity Act', *JAMA Pediatrics* 173, no. 1 (2019): 68–74, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2018.3416>.

⁹⁰ Emma Pitchforth et al., 'What and How Can We Learn from Complex Global Problems for Antimicrobial Resistance Policy? A Comparative Study Combining Historical and Foresight Approaches', *Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance* 35 (December 2023): 110–21, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2023.08.019>.

I think that we have a far better chance of policing AMR than we have of policing climate change.

- SE Some of these bigger global challenges... we work in four-year political cycles in our economies. We've seen just how disconnected that is just from the life cycle. I think it's sad that multilateralism is in the state that it is in at the moment on issues such as this.
- CG That's not going to improve.
- SE Yeah, not anytime soon, but on the pull side it was noted earlier that pathogens don't respect borders. Actually multinational pharmaceutical companies are highly globalized entities, right, and yet the community worked for years trying to find a global solution to rectify the bad economics here. That didn't materialize. I was part of that failure. We were unable to put a global mechanism in place that would rectify this. That would have been the ultimate solution, of course. And now we're left with what I was alluding to earlier: tracking national governments as they try to do this at a national level. That is obviously a much more challenging way now in the situation with pull incentives. Are we actually pulling on the same products? Are we sending the same message? Are they of sufficient value? It is obviously much more difficult for the governments to coordinate and to send a coherent message. But yes, I agree with you that AMR is probably easier to tackle than climate change.
- OG I just want to comment on the idea of comparing AMR to global climate change. But I think that living as a society, we are still not there. I mean, people are not conscious. And there also needs to be a lot of push forward from society in general. Demand of change needs to be supported financially to some extent if we want to have a global action. The perceptions that you have in the more developed countries are going to be completely different from the real, real drama that we are seeing in the low and medium-income countries. That's the difficulty in how to address the challenge globally. I'm not so much optimistic that in the short term we will see an effective turn, bending the curve in terms of how we want to respond to the different challenges.

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